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D2.2 - digiNEB.eu web platform, Rel. 2.0

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
CTA	Call-To-Action
DEP	Digital Europe Programme
DMS	Document Management System
DTPC	Deputy Technical Project Coordinator
EAG	External Advisory Group
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FACL	Financial & Administrative Coordinator Leader
GA	Grant Agreement
HP	HomePage
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KOM	Kick-off meeting
NEB	New European Bauhaus
PMB	Project Management Board
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
SSO	Single Sign-On
TBD	To be defined
The Consortium	All the Project Partners, viz. TU DELFT + Trust-IT + COMMpla + EAAE + ICF + IW
The Project Beneficiaries	The signatory Partners of the Grant Agreement, viz. TU DELFT + Trust-IT + EAAE + ICF + IW
TL	Task Leader
TPC	Technical Project Coordinator
TWG	Thematic Working Group
UI	User Interface
UP	User Profile
UX	User Experience
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Keywords

Website; Web platform; New European Bauhaus; UX; UI; Digital Toolkit, Observatory; eLearning Platform.

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Executive Summary

This document summarises the current characteristics of the digiNEB.eu website, in the context of its second release – Rel. 2.0 – completed in June 2023, in line with the Grant Agreement. While the first version of the digiNEB.eu website was delivered in Month 1 (October 2022) of the project, as documented in D2.1 “digiNEB.eu web platform, Rel. 1.0”, a continuous path of evolution has been followed, owing to the agile methodology adopted by the developing team at Trust-IT and COMMpla. This has led to the completion of the second release of the platform (Rel. 2.0), as presented in this document. A third and final release of the digiNEB.eu website is planned for Month 18 (March 2024), and it will be described in D2.4 “digiNEB.eu web platform, Rel. 3.0”.

The main purpose of the digiNEB.eu platform is to technically support the development of a digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus, which is the central mission of the digiNEB.eu initiative. The website is also the communication hub and main channel of the digiNEB.eu initiative to engage with targeted stakeholders and turn them into users and active members of the community in coordination with the other communication channels and engagement mechanisms of the wider NEB movement. As such, the digiNEB.eu website also provides core content and messages to inform relevant stakeholders about the project, disseminate relevant results and offer them the opportunity to access NEB digital solutions, and it will be a central element in supporting digiNEB.eu’s sustainability strategy.

The digiNEB.eu platform is SEO-driven, follows UX and UI principles and provides the required support to a series of other tasks of the digiNEB.eu’s work plan, namely in WP2, WP3, WP4, and also WP5. Lastly, it supports the digiNEB.eu Consortium in complying with the GDPR and the project’s Data Management Plan, and it is designed to allow for performance assessment and web analytics monitoring.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Scope

This document presents the updated structure and the planned evolution of the **digiNEB.eu web platform**. Release 2.0 of the platform – formally delivered at the end of Month 9 of the Project (30 June 2023), but reflecting actions carried out since Month 4 (January 2023) on the previous major release (Rel. 1.0) of the web platform active at www.digineb.eu since October 2022 – represents the platform in its current state, with relevant evolutions compared to Rel. 1.0, including:

- digiNEB.eu **eLearning catalogue and platform**;
- Consolidated **digital hub** (toolkit and observatory);
- New digital processes for **registration and contribution/co-creation** from end-users;
- **UX/UI** improvements throughout the platform, including the outcomes from stakeholders and end-users;
- Updated **privacy policy** and **intellectual property** sections.

Any ulterior changes to the digiNEB.eu web platform, especially those arising from end-users' needs and comments that will be recorded in the coming weeks and months, will be accounted for in the next and final version of the platform, i.e., Rel. 3.0, which will be released in Month 18 (March 2024).

This document results from a meticulous feedback collection process, including contributions from the digiNEB.eu's consortium and from external users – through an anonymous survey involving over 300 unique community members and a UX workshop, held on 13 June 2023, involving eight experts representing the project's stakeholder groups (see Sections 3.2, 3.3, and 3.4). To effectively elaborate this data, the document was submitted in August 2023 rather than by the contractual date of 30 June 2023, as established in the Grant Agreement /1/.

1.2 Structure of the document

The document is structured as follows:

- Section 2 summarises the website's main features as of Rel. 2.0 (June 2023).
- Section 3 presents the digiNEB.eu website's evolution path leading to this Release 2.0, detailing how the platform has improved (layout and navigation, graphics, tools, and functionalities) during the first nine months of the project and how feedback from partners and end-users were gathered and addressed.
- Section 4 highlights the technical details of Rel. 2.0, providing an overview of the user profiles, privileges, user journeys, and personas identified for the web platform. It also displays some elements of the design development process adopted from a UX/UI standpoint.
- Section 5 describes the website's maintenance principles.
- Section 6 updates on data management, privacy and terms of use adopted at www.digineb.eu, outlining the relations of the web platform with aspects of data management plan and ethics.
- Section 7 details the further modifications implemented following the recommendations received at the project's Interim Review on December 2023. These include some minor changes in the website's Privacy Policy and Terms of Use plus a detailed hand over of the platform to consortium partner TU Delft.
- Finally, Section 8 provides the main conclusions, and Section 9 includes the main references for this document.

1.3. Relation with other project deliverables

The following deliverables of digiNEB.eu are closely related to this document:

- D1.1 “Project Handbook”, 12 December 2022.
- D1.2 “Data Management Plan”, 13 December 2022.
- D1.3 “Ethics Report, Year 1”, 4 October 2023.
- D2.1 “digiNEB.eu web platform, Rel. 1.0”, 16 December 2022.
- D4.1 “Stakeholder engagement plan and adoption & monitoring report – initial version”, 1 February 2023.
- D5.1 “Plan for dissemination, exploitation, communication activities (DECP)”, 9 May 2023.

2. Main features of the digiNEB.eu platform

Rel. 2.0 of the digiNEB.eu web platform was completed in M09 of the project (June 2023) after a sequence of incremental developments conducted on Rel. 1.0, which was formally delivered as early as December 2022.

As the platform supports the project's digital processes and engages target stakeholders, this new Release 2.0 has been updated in adherence to the digiNEB.eu work plan to further expand the functionalities offered to the various categories of end-users, improve the user interface and better facilitate the promotion and communication of digiNEB.eu results, aligning with the values of the overall NEB community.

As of today, the digiNEB.eu web platform is characterised by the following main "modules":

- **Communications hub:** Over the first nine months of the project, the platform has consolidated its role as the project's prime engagement and communication tool (particularly, in so doing, the platform has also provided a virtual space in direct support of Task 5.1 (dissemination and communication) and Task 4.1 (stakeholder engagement), allowing for the publication of technical content from multiple actors, including end-users. This has been accomplished thanks to the launching of several features listed below, which have been continuously improved through an agile approach, addressing the feedback received from external users and consortium partners (more details in Sec. 3 below). The platform's features and services have been continuously improved in compliance with UX principles.
- **Digital Toolkit:** This is a fundamental module developed to support the digitalisation of the NEB community, bringing together digital solution providers and end-users. The digiNEB.eu platform currently provides access to 250+ digital solutions that the NEB ecosystem can adopt. Set up at the onset of digiNEB.eu (October 2022), the digital toolkit has been designed as an easily browsable catalogue following UX principles. Owing to the 'open' nature of the Toolkit, digital solutions can be added either by Consortium Partners or directly by providers and end-users themselves. Already several users met by digiNEB.eu Consortium Partners at both virtual and physical events have been successfully involved, and, in this sense, the realisation of the digital toolkit is a practical example of a NEB co-creation best practice.
- **Observatory:** The digiNEB.eu website aims to become a relevant, impartial 'observatory' supporting the digitalisation of NEB. For this reason, the central part of the web platform's homepage continuously and automatically 'pushes' the most relevant elements of content published in the various sections of the site, including success stories, news pieces, events, relevant passages discussed by community members in the thematic working groups (TWGs), and more. The procedures embedded in the platform by which the items are published as part of the 'observatory' are rule-based and, at the moment, include the parameters 'date' and "feedback from end-users" (e.g., number of *likes* on a post, comments). The system is fully parametric so that in the future other "rules" can be added to best adapt the performance of the observatory to serve the objectives of the project.
- **Thematic Working Groups (TWG):** Since M04 (January 2023), the digiNEB.eu website supports the work performed by four Thematic Working Groups (namely: Design and Architecture, Production and Construction, Verticals, and Community & Sustainability). These have been set up on digiNEB.eu by means of the Flarum software (www.flarum.org). Flarum, an open-source solution, allows the provisioning of a forum space for discussions and comment feeds on the main TWG topics, actively monitored by moderators. The various functionalities of the digiNEB.eu forum, aka TWGs, providing seamless integration with the digiNEB.eu platform,

deliver a smooth UX for the digiNEB.eu community that will be reached out to by the responsible Partners and constitute a potentially robust engagement lever for the end-users, who can collaborate enjoying a smooth UX (SSO with the rest of the platform's functionalities). Further feedback from the end-users should allow to evolve the tool's functionalities and workflow as part of Rel. 3.0 of the platform.

- **eLearning module ("Training" section):** Launched in M07 (April 2023), the "Training" section of the platform combines both the macro-functionality of a catalogue of courses and of a full-fledged eLearning platform based on the [TRUST-LCMS product](#). In this customised implementation realised for digiNEB.eu, the "training" section, on the one hand, offers convenient access to a catalogue of eLearning courses designed to foster knowledge sharing within the NEB community and, on the other hand, it supports hosting SCORM courses, all delivering a seamless UX for the users (including SSO, release of training certificates, and training progress in their dashboards). The catalogue is integrated into the Drupal CMS and allows the user to publish selected training material, hereby expressly including courses available at websites worldwide (so-called "external resources"). In fact, while third parties host some of the titles available in the catalogue, the eLearning module also allows training courses in the catalogue to be fully hosted by digiNEB.eu (so-called "internal resources"). This is thanks to the e-Learning module deployed, a customised instance of Moodle-based eLearning platform (based on Moodle 4.1.2+ www.moodle.org) deployed and freely accessible at www.digineb.eu. The eLearning platform was officially opened to the public on April 2023, with just the Trust-IT team, as website administrators, able to add courses to the catalogue. Then, since July 2023, all digiNEB.eu partners could autonomously add training modules through their moderator's account personal dashboard. The training platform is built with an inclusive approach: it is open to freely registered users and supports authors and organisations willing to offer their courseware to audiences interested in the digitalisation of NEB and NEB at large. Finally, it also allows registered users to openly access internal training programs, browse digiNEB.eu news and events, register for informative newsletters ads (for further information, see the [terms of use of digiNEB.eu](#)). This inclusive approach allows to enhance the offerings available to NEB actors. The catalogue will feature both courses available via external websites and those directly usable on digiNEB.eu platform. WP3 "Pan-EU capacity building" is responsible for populating the catalogue (with both external and internal resources), with a target of reaching over 1,000 trainees.
- **Early Adopters Network¹:** Since M04 (January 2023), the website has also supported one of the main instruments to recruit ambassadors of the digiNEB.eu project. In this Rel. 2.0 the Early Adopters section supports the digital process (and related database) for candidates to apply to become Early Adopters, a functionality widely discussed with the other Consortium Partners. Overall, the goal is to entice new candidates to join the Early Adopters group while giving the deserved visibility to those who have already been granted the early adopter status.
- **External Advisory Group (EAG):** The digiNEB.eu platform also hosts The Expert Advisory Group (EAG), which comprises esteemed professionals from various disciplines of the built environment, including creative industries, accessibility, architecture, design, and construction materials. The section dedicated to the EAG indicated as "Advisors" is, in this new Rel.2.0, located in the "about" section of the website.

¹ An "Early Adopter" is a digiNEB.eu user that wants to actively participate in the digital ecosystem of NEB and that act as a project's promoter to help increase the visibility of digiNEB.eu throughout the NEB community and vice versa.

Each of the macro-functionalities above is effectively an “**asset**” of digiNEB.eu. Each of those assets needs to be leveraged to support achieving the project’s goals and create the expected impact. This represents a strong vantage point for digiNEB.eu, in that, without any delay in the project’s timeline, all the tools and macro-functionalities are indicated in digiNEB.eu’s Grant Agreement (GA) /[1](#)/ have been successfully delivered. In the coming months, these resources and functionalities will allow the Consortium to direct its resources in populating the platform with the rich content and opportunities envisaged to achieve the level of engagement of the community indicated by the Grant Agreement and the subsequent project deliverables, particularly D4.1 “Stakeholder engagement plan and adoption & monitoring report – initial version”, and D5.1 “Plan for dissemination, exploitation, communication activities (DECP)”. Such technical content will also be the prime ingredient to drive organic traffic, also via SEO activities.

While other sections and functionalities are available on the website, the hierarchy of the various user categories and other technical details are discussed in Sec. 3.

Lastly, the planned **Release 3.0 at the ²end of the ‘validation’ phase of the project (M18, i.e. March 2024)** will further improve the web presence of digiNEB.eu, leveraging engaging content and active months of user interaction and feedback.

² As of 3 August 2023, the digiNEB.eu website has achieved a Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) score of 92%, according to Google’s Lighthouse webpage auditing tool. The 92% SEO score for digiNEB.eu signifies effective optimisation and adherence to key SEO practices, including responsive design, quick load times, and structured content. Such optimisation is expected to hold (and potentially further improve) when more technical content will be uploaded on the platform, thereby boosting the visibility of digiNEB.eu in search engine results, ultimately leading to increased organic traffic.

3. Evolution path

3.1 From Rel. 1.0 to Rel. 2.0

While the first version of the website has been online since October 2022 (Month 1 of the project), and Release 1.0 was made available to all users in December 2022, the digiNEB.eu web platform completed its second major release (Rel. 2.0) in June 2023, i.e., M09 of the project.

With respect to Rel.1.0, Release 2.0 is enriched with tools, digital processes, and content that are beneficial to the NEB community in adherence to the plans described in the Grant Agreement /1/. It has also been improved from the UX point of view, also addressing feedback from partners and end-users to better engage the project’s diverse community of stakeholders.

In more detail, Rel. 2.0 of the digiNEB.eu web platform features the following:

1. **Improved presentation of the digiNEB.eu initiative** with its direct role in supporting the NEB initiative.
2. **Evolved releases of the observatory and the digital toolkit** arising from the early release distributed as part of Rel. 1.1 - available since early January 2023.
3. **First release of TWG pages providing open discussion forums and collaboration virtual spaces among digiNEB.eu community members.** These were delivered in February 2023 as part of Rel. 1.2 and are implemented by means of a customised instance of the open software FLARUM (www.flarum.org), which also provides SSO with the rest of the platform’s functionalities.
4. **First release of the eLearning catalogue and platform** in M07 (6 April 2023), as part of Rel. 1.3, delivering an environment open to selected user profiles.
5. **Revised digital process for application as digiNEB.eu Early Adopter.**
6. **Updated personal profile page**, allowing users to create an account and navigate the website, plus enriching its different catalogues (digital toolkit, success stories, eLearning platform)
7. **Interactive timeline** detailing the project’s evolution to the website visitors with the possibility to Zoom in on milestones or events accomplished monthly.

The diagram below shows the overall evolution timeline (24 months) of the digiNEB.eu web platform is represented.

Figure 1 – Evolution timeline of the digiNEB.eu web platform

Overall, this Rel. 2.0 of the digiNEB.eu website delivers all the main functionalities expected by the Grant Agreement, it refines the visual identity of the project in line with the [visual identity guidelines provided by the EC for their NEB initiative](#), and it accounts for a first, comprehensive round of feedback from real end-users, gathered via a public survey and a workshop from external users, besides less structured comments received in other occasions.

The digiNEB.eu website is accessible at <https://digineb.eu/>, and some selected print screens of its main sections released in M02 (November 2022) and M09 (June 2023) are visible below for a quick comparison.

Figure 2 – Selected print screens of various sections of digiNEB.eu website as of November 2022

Figure 3 – Selected print screens of various sections of the digiNEB.eu website as of June 2023

Colours and visuals of the digiNEB.eu website has evolved over time, addressing internal and external feedback received during different release iterations. As also mentioned in Sec. 2, future evolutions and refinements will be implemented to ensure that any remaining visualisation issues will be addressed, favouring the creation of an increasingly inclusive platform. Issues encountered by people with visual impairment will also be analysed and addressed, either as part of the sustainability roadmap (Task 5.3) or, wherever possible (compatibly with the resources available), during this Task 2.1 of the project.

The third and conclusive iteration of the digiNEB.eu web platform – Rel. 3.0 – will be released in M18 (March 2024). This version will build upon the already implemented modifications and be enriched with digital content beneficial for the NEB community. It will further exploit its main assets – Digital Toolkit, Observatory, and eLearning catalogue and platform. The content, in particular, will support the refinement of the SEO, driving a larger userbase to the platform. One more minor release of the platform is also expected in M12. Both Rel. 2.1 and Rel. 3.0 will be described in depth in D2.4 “digiNEB.eu web platform, Rel. 3.0”.

The table below outlines the platform’s main evolution thus far and the next steps.

Minor release	Major release	Main features	Delivery date	Status
Rel. 0.1		Initial web presence: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Instance in Drupal 9 • Project’s description, including objectives and target services • Webform for sounding out Early Adopters • First release of the Digital Toolkit 	M01 (Oct 2022)	Delivered
	Rel. 1.0	First version of the web platform: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early release of the Observatory 	M03 (Dec 2022)	Delivered (D2.1)
Rel. 1.1		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revised release of the Observatory (the consolidated version arising from the early release distributed in December 2022) 	M04 (Jan 2023)	Delivered
Rel. 1.2		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launch of the TWG module (January 2023) • Implementation of user feedback • Revised UX 	M05 (Feb 2023)	Delivered
Rel. 1.3		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First release of the eLearning catalogue and platform (planned for M06, March 2023 - delivered on 6 April 2023) 	M07 (Apr 2023)	Delivered
	Rel. 2.0	Intermediate version of the web platform: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of further user feedback, including outcomes from Survey #1 and from Workshop with External Users #1 • Consolidated back-end (Drupal Version 9.5.10), with security patches 	M09 (Jun 2023)	Delivered (D2.2)
Rel. 2.1		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Addressing possible ethics & privacy issues, as part of D1.3 “Ethics Report” (due in Sep 2023) • Improving users’ dashboard and other UX/UI touch-ups (including to TWGs) 	M13 (Oct 2023)	Planned
	Rel. 3.0	Final version of the web platform: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Final release of the Digital Toolkit, including improved search functionalities • Final release of the Observatory • Final release of eLearning catalogue & platform • Addressing outcomes from Survey #2 and from Workshop with External Users #2 • Publication of the digiNEB.eu Roadmap • Policy recommendations coming from TWGs 	M18 (Mar 2024)	Planned (D2.4)

Table 1 – Evolution path of the website

3.2 Training sessions and partners' feedback

One central step leading to the realisation of Rel. 2.0 of the web platform consisted in continuously gathering input from consortium partners, collecting their comments and gathering feedback on their user experience with the platform. As part of that process, the Trust-IT team offered several internal training sessions to train consortium members to familiarise themselves with the platform, both the front-end interface and the backend operational dashboard. These sessions were held on:

- 5 December 2022,
- 7 December 2022 (two sessions), and
- 11 January 2023.

Moreover, since February 2023, feedback from partners on the website was systematically collected in an internally shared spreadsheet structured by COMMpla ("digiNEB.eu digital HUB Comments for Rel. 2.0"). As part of that activity, 88 entries were collected, of which 32 were from EAAE, 20 from TU DELFT, 1 from IW, and 35 from Trust-IT/COMMpla.

Figure 4 – Total website feedback entries from digiNEB.eu partners

Of those 88 entries, 67 were addressed, 15 are currently in progress (4 are being implemented, 2 are on the to-do list, and 9 need further internal discussions) and the remaining 6 ones were blocked either because further discussions within the consortium were needed or because they were considered non-actionable (e.g., because of a low benefit-to-effort ratio, considering the limited effort budget available to this task of the digiNEB.eu initiative).

Figure 5 – Status of website feedback entries from digiNEB.eu partners

Below, a table resuming the main points in the partners' feedback spreadsheet is provided (for further information, see the full table in [Appendix A](#)).

Type of issue	Total Number	Impact		Status		
		Front-end	Back-end	Done	In Progress	Blocked
Website UI/UX	14	12	2	8	5	1
Homepage	15	14	1	10	5	
Digital Toolkit	28	5	23	22	2	4
Observatory	1	1		1		
Success Stories	9	2	7	9		
eLearning	13	8	5	10	3	
TWG	2	2		1		1
News	1	1		1		
Early Adopters	2		2	2		
EAG	3	3		3		
GRAND TOTAL	88	48	40	67	15	6
%	100%	53%	47%	77%	14%	9%

Table 2 – Rolling partners’ feedback spreadsheet on the web platform (snapshot as of 14 June 2023)

Considering the continuative nature of the web platform development task, further queries from the digiNEB.eu partners and external users (see Sec. 3.3 and 3.4) will continue to be collected and addressed, inasmuch as the residual effort on Task 2.1 available for Rel. 3.0 will allow it.

3.3 Anonymous survey #1

After addressing queries and comments from consortium members, which eventually led to Rel. 1.2 and Rel. 1.3, a short multiple-answer survey was circulated among a unique list of over 300 contacts to collect feedback from the digiNEB.eu community of users. This pool of people was selected among the community members who had adhered to the project’s privacy policy. These included users registered to the platform, event attendees, and newsletter registrants.

The survey's final aim was to enhance the web platform and cater to the unique needs of digiNEB.eu diverse community, optimising the website's ability to provide relevant and comprehensive information about digital products for architects, designers, and engineers aligned with the New European Bauhaus (NEB) principles.

The survey included questions on features and functionalities, helpfulness and value, as well as any aspects of the website that may be confusing or difficult to navigate. Visual design and aesthetics evaluations as well as technical issues such as speed, performance, and responsiveness of the platform, were also included. The final questions tackled the overall satisfaction with the user experience, the current offer of digital products, and the likelihood of recommending the website to others interested in the New European Bauhaus. The first part of the digital process implemented on the platform to support Website Survey #1 is shown in the figure below.

Take part in our survey and help us improve digiNEB.eu

The digiNEB.eu consortium firmly believes in the power of collaboration and values the insights and feedback of its expert community.

This is why if you have enjoyed using or plan to use our platform and would like to contribute to its improvement, we kindly request that you spare **just three minutes** of your time to complete the survey below.

Your **valuable feedback** will contribute to transforming our platform into an online co-creation space that meets the unique needs of our diverse community.

How well does the digiNEB.eu website meet your expectations in terms of providing relevant and comprehensive information about the digital products for architects, designers, and engineers working with the New European Bauhaus (NEB) principles?
1 poorly met; 5 exceptionally met

1
 2
 3
 4
 5

Please tell us more! You can explain your vote here:

Next >

Figure 6 – Website survey #1 (sample)

As of mid-June 2023, 19 usable results were collected (a 6% response rate), and key trends and recommendations were extracted and analysed. Below, a question-by-question analysis of the comment is provided. Although the number is still quantitatively low, the survey provides valuable indications and it will remain open and eventually evolve into User Survey #2, where a larger base of community members will share further feedback and suggest potential future improvements.

Q1. How well does the digiNEB.eu website meets your expectations in terms of providing relevant and comprehensive information about the digital products for architects, designers, and engineers working with the New European Bauhaus (NEB) principles? [score possible: from 1 to 5]

Average response rate: 3.9 out of 5.

Q2. What specific features or functionalities of the digiNEB.eu website do you find most helpful or valuable for your work in the New European Bauhaus (NEB) principles connected to digitalisation?

- The Observatory (5 mentions): The observatory feature is highly valued as it provides a centralised platform for accessing and disseminating information related to the NEB principles connected to digitalisation. Users find it helpful to stay updated with the latest trends, research findings, and policy developments in sustainable design and construction.
- Success Stories (4 mentions): The success stories section is considered valuable for showcasing real-life examples of innovative digital solutions that align with NEB principles.

- Thematic Working Groups (4 mentions): The availability of thematic working groups is appreciated by users as it offers opportunities for collaboration, knowledge sharing, and policy recommendations. These groups allow professionals from different stakeholder groups to come together, exchange ideas, and collectively work towards advancing the NEB principles in the context of digitalisation.
- Respondents valued the Digital Toolkit (3 mentions) as it provides users with a comprehensive collection of resources, tools, and digital solutions tailored to support their work in the New European Bauhaus principles connected to digitalization. This centralised repository offers innovative technologies, software applications, and design methodologies, empowering users to easily explore and integrate digital solutions into their projects and workflows.
- Training Services (2 mentions): Including training services is seen as a valuable feature for users seeking to enhance their skills and knowledge in sustainable design and digital solutions. Users appreciate the availability of training modules, courses, and capacity-building materials tailored to different stakeholder groups.

Q3. Are there any aspects of the digiNEB.eu website that you find confusing or difficult to navigate?

Over 60% of respondents found the digiNEB.eu website is easy to navigate. The remaining 40% indicated difficulties in navigating the website. Specific cases and adopted mitigation strategies are listed in the table below.

Type of issue	Feedback	Status	Mitigation
Navigation and Menu	Main menu (header) is confusing and inconsistent in terms of linking to different pages and sections	Done	Header was fixed following also website UX workshop #1
Navigation and Menu	Platform link needs to be redirected to a dedicated page to explain its goals and sections clearly	Done	This was implemented as part of Rel. 2.0 where the main Top Menu was changed
Navigation and Menu	The menu should remain fixed on all pages and not float or move, ensuring consistent navigation experience	Blocked	The menu is already fixed
Navigation and Menu	Thoroughly checking links to ensure correct navigation between pages and sections	Done	Through check was carried out and over 10 navigation issues fixed
About Section	Expand the about menu to include additional topics that effectively showcase and emphasise the project structure, vision, roadmap, etc.	Done	The About section was expanded with more sections dedicated to NEB and the digiNEB.eu project.
Homepage Enhancement	Utilise the homepage's background B/W video to highlight important news and updates	Blocked	This was deemed as not applicable as the hero section already contains a subsection listing the main

Type of issue	Feedback	Status	Mitigation
			highlights
Homepage Enhancement	Reverse the order of EVENTS and NEWS sections on the homepage to align with the NEWS & EVENTS section	Done	Reverse was implemented in Rel. 2.0
Thematic Working Groups (TWGs)	Enhance TWG navigation by displaying different groups when hovering over the TWG topic in the menu, including an option for "ALL TWG"	TBD	Will be addressed once more content will be available in the TWGs
Thematic Working Groups (TWGs)	Provide an easy way to navigate back to the digiNEB.eu website from independent TWG pages	Done	Shortcut was implemented
Facilitation and Engagement	Designate and present a moderator/facilitator for each TWG and introduce them with profiles, including a photo, to encourage engagement and participation	TBD	An updated version of the TWG pages will be presented in Rel. 2.1, once content will increase

Table 3 – Navigability issues feedback from anonymous survey #1

Q4. How would you rate the visual design and aesthetics of the digiNEB.eu website? (From 1 to 5)

Average response rate: 4.0 out of 5.

Q5. Is there anything you would suggest changing or improving in terms of design?

Type of issue	Feedback	Status	Mitigation
Visual Presentation	Make posts like "your success story" more visual by reducing the use of logos and stock photos	Blocked	Not applicable as images are provided by success stories providers. However, graphic improvements could be further implemented, as written consent is sought from success stories providers
Visual Presentation	Ensure that basic information is clearly displayed on the main page cards, allowing users to understand the	Done	Cards display was changed, and flipping eliminated

Type of issue	Feedback	Status	Mitigation
	content without the need to click further		
Clarity and Content Accessibility	Avoid the excessive use of abbreviations at the top of the page, as it may initially confuse users. Instead, use clear phrases or contents to facilitate easy navigation and understanding	Done	TWG and EAG abbreviations were removed
Clarity and Content Accessibility	Consider incorporating a section with small tips related to the New European Bauhaus (NEB) initiative, providing helpful guidance to users	Done	A section was added in the About menu section
Colour Accessibility	Take into consideration colour blindness issues by ensuring that colour choices, particularly for important elements such as buttons, are easily distinguishable	TBD	Further discussions within the consortium are needed in order to implement this step
Coherence and Navigation	Improve differentiation in how various topics are presented to create a visually coherent and organised design	Done	Menu was reshaped following various indications in the multiple feedback items
Coherence and Navigation	Enhance site organisation and navigation to make it easier for users to find relevant content	Done	Same as above
Homepage Enhancement	Further exploration and improvements on the homepage can contribute to a better user experience, potentially addressing issues such as content layout, information hierarchy, and visual appeal	Done	Homepage was enhanced following several indications received before

Table 4 – Design issues feedback from anonymous survey #1

Overall, given the recursive appearance of queries related to website navigation, homepage and menu, the second workshops and the consequent Release 3.0 will seek to further enhance these platform’s sections and its overall navigability.

Q 6-7. Have you encountered any technical difficulties while using the digiNEB.eu website? Please specify:

From the answers provided, 75% of respondents have not encountered any technical difficulties while using the digiNEB.eu website. This suggests that the website has been generally stable and user-friendly for most users. Only 25% of respondents mentioned experiencing navigation problems, although no further specification was provided.

Overall, the relatively low number of technical difficulties reported is a positive indication that the digiNEB.eu website is functioning well for the majority of users. However, the mentioned navigation and functionality issues should be taken into consideration to optimise the website and provide an enhanced user experience for all visitors in an expanding user base.

Q8-9. Are there any specific digital products or categories that you feel are lacking on our website? Please provide details on what you would like to see included.

Based on the responses, the following trends could be observed:

No: over 60% of respondents indicated that they do not feel any specific digital products or categories are lacking on the website. They seem thus satisfied with the current offerings or believe that the website adequately covers their needs.

Yes: over 35% of respondents felt that some specific digital products or categories were lacking on the website. Unfortunately, further details were not provided, so it was unclear which specific areas they believed were lacking.

Type of issue	Feedback	Status	Mitigation
Inclusion of small cities	Respondents emphasised the importance of showcasing digital solutions and success stories from small cities, which often face unique challenges and can benefit from tailored digital tools and resources	Blocked	Not applicable: success stories linked to the application of digital solutions in small cities are already included in the digital toolkit (e.g., Duved Future) and are likely to grow further as new solutions and best practices are recorded. A filter entry targeting, for instance, small centres, could be added to the Success Stories search bar once more content is available (Rel. 3.0)
Accessibility guide and usability	The demand for an accessibility guide or category that provides information on navigating and using the website effectively emerged	TBD	A video series on how to upload digital solutions to the platform will be produced in the following months
Nature and biodiversity in Thematic Working Groups (TWGs)	There is a suggestion to integrate the dimension of nature and biodiversity into the description of the TWG focused on community and sustainability	Blocked	Most digital solutions included in the toolkit and success stories explicitly target sustainability - a core NEB principle. However, nature and biodiversity could be more explicitly targeted when elaborating the content of the community and sustainability TWG.

Table 5 – Navigability lacking products feedback from anonymous survey #1

Q10. How would you rate the speed and performance of our website? Do you find it responsive and quick to load?

Average response rate: 4.6 out of 5.

Q11. Overall, how satisfied are you with the user experience of the digiNEB.eu website?

Average response rate: 4.1 out of 5.

From the specific feedback, the following risk factors were identified and mitigated.

Type of issue	Feedback	Status	Mitigation
Lack of clarity in the navigation	It is recommended to provide clearer descriptions or explanations of TWG and EAG to improve understanding of these terms	Done	TWG and EAG abbreviations were removed and inserted as full names in subsections
Content modelling workshops	It is suggested to conduct content modelling workshops to define and refine the content strategy for the website	Done	A dedicated UX/UI workshop was organised as indicated in the next section (3.3)
Customer journeys and UX research	Building customer journeys based on UX research identifying the identified target audiences can enhance the user experience	Done	Same as above

Table 6 – UX feedback from anonymous survey #1

Q12. How likely are you to recommend the digiNEB.eu website to a colleague or someone within your network who is interested in the New European Bauhaus? [answers allowed: Very likely, likely, unlikely, very unlikely]

The responses indicate a positive sentiment and a strong likelihood of recommendation. Here is the analysis of the answers:

- 80% of respondents expressed a higher confidence level, stating they are "Very Likely" to recommend the digiNEB.eu website.
- 20% of respondents indicated they are "Likely" to recommend the website.

In a context of a still limited userbase (as expected, considering the project is still in its early phase and there is still a limited amount of content available on the website to drive users' interest and gain visibility in organic searches on the web), the responses indicated above highlight a high level of satisfaction and appreciation of the initiative among the survey participants, suggesting that they find value in the website's content and services related to digitalisation effort in support of the New European Bauhaus. The positive feedback and intention to recommend the website indicate that it is seen as a valuable resource within their professional networks.

A second and final survey is envisaged towards the end of 2023 (see Fig. 1 "Evolution timeline of the digiNEB.eu web platform"). Again, it will be coupled with a subsequent UX workshop#2. This will allow further expansion of the user base providing feedback in view of the final web platform release, scheduled for March 2024.

3.4 UX workshop #1

To collect further input from both consortium partners and external users, two UX workshops were organised by Trust-IT. The first one with "internal users", scheduled for 9 May 2023, ultimately did not take place. Although this is an unfortunate circumstance, we are convinced that this is not a great harm in the path of website evolution, as the "rolling website feedback spreadsheet" document already gathered plenty of feedback from the partners, certainly sufficient to capture their point of view on the website. In fact, far more articulate feedback was also gathered in the previous months

every week, especially from internal users (and also from external users), which also contributed to the fine-tuning process of the web platform, including from the back-end point of view.

Extremely relevant for the evolution of the platform is the feedback gathered from the “external” userbase, an element that is definitely going to be more statistically relevant in the near future, as the daily visits to the website will grow as an effect of the communication and dissemination activities on the content published on the website.

In order to start that in an organic way (extemporary feedback from external end-users has been gathered and utilised since the very first version of the platform was put online back in October 2022), one external workshop with end-users was held online on 13 June 2023 (starting at 10 am and lasting three hours). In order to keep the dialogue with the required level of interactivity, it was organised with an attendance of eight people representing the project’s main stakeholder categories (i.e., architects, designers, engineers, researchers, policymakers, and digital tech companies). This size is quite usual in similar workshops we have been organising for projects of equivalent complexity. The event, coordinated by 4 specialists from Trust-IT and COMMpla, aimed at gathering valuable feedback from members connected to the New European Bauhaus and the digital world, bringing in elements of a co-creation process, an approach also supported by the NEB’s principles.

The objectives of UX workshop #1 with representatives of the end-user categories of the digiNEB.eu website was to gain insights into the required features, evaluate the existing design, and assess the clarity of page elements, all utilising a virtual whiteboard to facilitate collaborative feedback and ideation. Those objectives aimed to support the enhancement of the user experience by incorporating user preferences and improving the usability aspects of the website. Below, further details of the workshop’s four main steps are provided:

1. **Gathering feedback on required features:** The workshop aimed to collect insights and opinions from the end users regarding the features they require on the website. This feedback helps in understanding the specific needs and expectations of the users, enabling the design team to prioritise and implement the most relevant features.
2. **Evaluating the current design:** The workshop sought to assess the effectiveness of the current design of key pages, including the digital solutions catalogue, use cases, and e-learning sections. By involving the end-user representatives, the workshop aimed to obtain their feedback on the design elements and overall user experience. This evaluation helps identify areas of improvement and ensures that the design aligns with the users' preferences and usability expectations.
3. **Assessing clarity of page elements:** The workshop aimed to determine the clarity and comprehensibility of various elements on the pages, such as result cards, filtering options, and the navigational menu. The workshop intended to identify any issues or confusion users might encounter while interacting with these elements by seeking feedback from the end users. This assessment helps in refining the design to make it more intuitive and user-friendly.
4. **Virtual whiteboard activities:** The workshop utilised a virtual whiteboard as a collaborative platform for engaging participants. This platform allowed participants to actively contribute ideas, share feedback, and collaborate on design improvements. The workshop fostered a productive and inclusive environment for collecting and organising feedback by leveraging the virtual whiteboard.

Figure 7 – Sample of the mural from the UX workshop #1

The main insights gathered from the workshop include the importance of a website with digital solutions for designers and architects, emphasising the need for interoperability and accessible data, a clear and easy-to-navigate menu, clarification on acronyms, addressing overlapping content in success stories and observatories, improving clarity on finding solutions and understanding the purpose of training, implementing filters in the toolkit based on sector, geographical deployment, TRL, and sustainability impact, incorporating certification options and credibility in the training platform, enhancing clarity and explicit calls-to-action in the observatory, improving metadata structure, providing clearer filters and explanations in the toolkit, including a wider range of end-user clusters, refining technology application fields, clarifying scores or ratings, better explaining the training package, and repositioning cards in the toolkit while including adopter names or links.

All the feedback above aligns with what was expected at this stage. Most comments were addressed by the Trust-IT tech team and are featured in Rel. 2.0. Other comments will be addressed in the coming months, also taking advantage of a larger amount of technical content uploaded in the platform (particularly training courses, technical discussions in the TWGs, success cases, etc.), and a few were deemed inappropriate or conflicted with GDPR/IP principles and therefore could not be addressed. **Overall, 53 main queries emerged from the UX/UI workshop #1, providing a good feedback basis to build upon.** These were categorised and analysed to organise the internal workflow. Among the queries, the main topics included the eLearning Platform (over 22%), the Digital Toolkit (over 20%)

and the success stories (about 19%). Other topics included the website menus, the Observatory, the Homepage, information architecture and other general queries.

Figure 8 – Website sections commented on during the UX/UI workshop #1 (values in percentage)

As shown in the figure below, of the 53 total issues collected, about **half (26) were readily addressed and implemented in Rel 2.0**. This activity has contributed to the overall improvement of the web platform, besides providing further user-supported evidence of the effectiveness of the various solutions adopted at digiNEB.eu.

In addition, 14 comments were **blocked** for the following reasons:

- **Out of scope/Redundancy:** Certain comments were deemed out of scope as they referred to different items or their listing display differed from the current setup. Therefore, these suggestions were not directly applicable to the workshop's focus and were not addressed.
- **Course provider discretion:** Certain suggestions related to courses and training material could not be implemented because they were dependent on external providers' discretion.
- **Possible UX/UI and IP problems:** Some comments raised concerns about potential UX/UI problems which might compromise a seamless user experience and lower the platform's accessibility.
- **IP problems:** Other comments could not be implemented because they infringed the intellectual property (IP) of external users, such as external solution providers, creating potential legal issues.
- **Redundancy:** Finally, some blocked comments also addressed issues already solved in previous website iterations.

An ulterior eight comments have been labelled as "to be defined" (**TBD**) and were postponed for future consideration. The main reason for designating them as TBD and targeting their implementation for Release 3.0 is the expectation that the project will mature and gain more content over time. Implementing these queries in a later release will allow for a more comprehensive and robust approach, acknowledging that certain features or improvements require additional time,

resources, or content development to be effectively integrated into the website. By deferring them to Release 3.0, the project team can focus on the immediate priorities and ensure a smoother rollout of the initial versions of the website. This approach allows for a phased and iterative development process, prioritising the initial releases’ most critical and essential features. As the project progresses and more content becomes available, the TBD queries will be revisited, refined, and eventually implemented in a future release, ensuring a more comprehensive and well-rounded user experience.

Finally, two issues linked to the eLearning Platform were classified as halfway between blocked and TBD, needing further technical discussions to understand their feasibility and further content to be fully implemented (if deemed doable).

Figure 9 – Status of website queries commented on during the UX/UI workshop #1 (numerical values)

Overall, the recent UX/UI workshop was a valuable opportunity to gather feedback to enrich the digiNEB.eu’s website. Representing various stakeholder categories, the attendees offered insights on required features, evaluated the current design, and assessed the clarity of page elements through a collaborative virtual whiteboard platform. The workshop underscored the importance of a website with digital solutions for architects and designers, emphasizing interoperability, accessibility, and navigability. The workshop’s insights and feedback led to numerous improvements implemented in Rel. 2.0, enhancing the platform’s value for the digiNEB.eu community and the overall user experience. Additionally, several queries were categorised for further consideration in future releases, fostering a phased and iterative development process to improve the platform's functionalities and overall user experience.

A second UX/UI workshop is envisaged towards the end of 2023 (see Fig. 1 “Evolution timeline of the digiNEB.eu web platform”). Again, it will be following a user survey. This will allow further expansion of the user base providing feedback in view of the final web platform release, scheduled for March 2024.

4. Technical details

4.1 Overview

The digiNEB.eu web platform is based on Drupal's open-source content management framework (www.drupal.org). More specifically, the website has been developed in Drupal 9, a stable version of the framework released by the Drupal community.

Drupal has been chosen for its wide spectrum of **functionalities**, supported by a large and qualified community of developers, which allows for complex customisations as requested by the digiNEB.eu project work plan and the ability to support different types of users and content (specific needs arising from the project's ambitious goals), besides its security features. Drupal natively allows authentication/authorisation **security management**, exploiting different roles, each linked to different privileges assigned to a specific group of users. The web platform team can assign different roles and authorisation levels to selected users as part of the website management activities. Drupal also can share selected content exposing API endpoints, thus allowing to reuse and show content outside the website, which is well in line with the scope of the NEB initiative.

The table below shows the main technical characteristics of the digiNEB.eu web platform, Rel. 2.0, online since June 2023 at www.digineb.eu.

Item	Details	Notes
CMS	Drupal 9.5.10	
Database	MySQL	
Web Server	Apache/2.4.52 (Ubuntu)	
PHP	8.1.2	
Thematic Working Groups (TWGs)	Flarum 1.5.0	Available since January 2023 (Rel. 1.2)
Digital Toolkit	Drupal view and moderation managed by Workbench	
Observatory	Drupal view and moderation managed by Workbench	Available since December 2022 (Rel. 1.1)
eLearning platform	Customised implementation of Moodle 4, and other technical modules (SSO, Catalogue, Certification module, graphical theme)	Publicly released on 4 April 2023 (Rel. 1.3)
Hosting	AWS (Amazon Web Services)	EC2 instance

Table 7 – Main technical features of Rel. 2.0 of the digiNEB.eu web platform

To give the users the functionality to bring forward the Thematic Working Groups that digiNEB.eu is going to support, the **Flarum** tool (www.flarum.org) has been selected and integrated with the Drupal instance of the web platform. Flarum is an OpenSource solution as minimal forum software with high extensibility. It is easy to extend using the available extension provided by the Flarum community or writing an owned extension as well. It is written in PHP and Typescript. Drupal uses the API of Flarum to import information about TWG discussion present to Flarum and use them in Drupal to build the Observatory together with other contents already present in Drupal. While anonymous users can read all content published on the TWGs, only registered users of www.digineb.eu can publish content on the TWGs.

A streamlined **registration process**, with an authentication step over the email address, has been implemented, by means of which is possible to create an account in digiNEB.eu to actively propose content for publication in various areas of the website (see also Sec. 4.3 “Website privileges and User Profiles (UPs)”). This is a fundamental way to engage the end-user community, in full respect of the

GDPR (acknowledgement of the privacy statement and terms of use is necessary for any end-user to receive access to her/his personal dashboard on www.digineb.eu) Drupal is used by Identity providers and, via Single SignOn, a user can use Flarum without recreating another user by exploiting the authentication/authorisation provided by Drupal.

With this Rel. 2.0, an **eLearning catalogue of courses and the related training platform** have been added to the web platform and are seamlessly integrated with the Drupal environment in terms of contents and learning paths suggested to the users. While the eLearning catalogue, displaying courses suggested by digiNEB.eu, is part of the Drupal frontend, the training platform supporting the locally stored courseware is based on Moodle (www.moodle.org). This configuration is a customised implementation of the TRUST-LCMS product, including single-sign-on features, personalised graphics, and digital processes to manage the learning paths and to issue to the trainee a digiNEB.eu-specific certification (<https://www.trust-itservices.com/products/trust-lcms>).

4.2 Drupal management

The CMS utilised in the development of the digiNEB.eu website is Drupal. More specifically, the Drupal 9.5.10 version is currently running. Nothing has changed since Release 1.0 as far as the Drupal development architecture is concerned.

For the website, a custom theme has been designed and developed by COMMpla to have maximum flexibility to handle the UI/UX of the website, depending on the requests to eventually address.

The homepage presents a video embedded in the background to limit the overload of the website at startup, giving the visitor much more graphic empathy, who can immediately appreciate the purpose/activities of the digiNEB.eu initiative. The video can be changed at will.

The sections where catalogue-like displays are present (e.g., Digital Toolkit, Training, Success Stories, Early adopter stories) have been developed exploiting the functionalities provided by the core module Views that enable it to perform sort of query on the content database of Drupal.

Sorting and Filtering capabilities have been combined with the Views core module and Better Exposed community module.

Each visualisation has been customised in the custom theme using TWIG programming language, the standard for theme customisation since Drupal 8.

The responsive management of the website is managed by SCSS compiled as CSS. All the JS and CSS assets have been minimised to limit the overload of the page. This gives less weight to the bundle executed by the browser, which is responsible for the UI of the website.

4.3 Website privileges and User Profiles (UPs)

The website provides different privileges to different users, depending on their engagement level with the platform. In fact, the platform offers the opportunity to its users to create an account, increase their access to functionalities and information and expand their interaction level with the platform.

The main roles that are assigned in the digiNEB.eu platform are listed in Table 8 and further detailed in the following paragraphs. The motivation for having 5 UPs derives directly from the different needs of adequately supporting the engagement strategy for the website without losing control over the quality of content published there.

User Profiles	Description	Privileges (increasing)
UP#1 - Anonymous visitor	No profile	Navigation
UP#2 - Community Member	Identified person with validated login & password	Accesses the full catalogue of courses. Has an online personal dashboard at digiNEB.eu. <u>Proposes</u> content in the TWGs, in the Early Adopters area, in the Success Stories, in the eLearning catalogue, and in the Digital Toolkit
UP#3 - Trusted Contributor	Trusted community member	Like UP#2, plus: <u>Publishes</u> content autonomously in the TWGs, in the Early Adopters area, in the Success Stories, in the eLearning catalogue, and in the Digital Toolkit
UP#4 - Moderator	Member of the digiNEB.eu Consortium and other selected individuals	Like UP#3, plus: Accesses as editor to the CMS of the web platform
UP#5 - Administrator	Selected members of the Trust-IT+COMMpla team	Like UP#4, plus: Manages the root password of the web platform

Table 8 – Description of the various User Profiles (UPs) available on the web platform

The **Anonymous visitor** is a user interested in the content published on the digiNEB.eu website and, for this reason, visits it regularly or sporadically. This type of user is just interested in getting to know the latest news, events, or digital solutions published on the digiNEB.eu website, but is not interested in publishing content online. We target over 50,000 unique visitors to digiNEB.eu by the end of the project (as of 15 July 2023, around 12,000 unique visitors have been recorded).

The **Community member** is a user that has created an account on the digiNEB.eu website and has been validated by the generation of a login and password. This user proposes new content to be published on the website, which is checked and validated by Moderators and Superusers. Currently, 46 people outside the digiNEB.eu consortium are acting as community members on the website

The **Trusted Contributor** is a trusted user that regularly publishes content in the Observatory or Digital Toolkit sections. The Contributor is a community member that has been upgraded thanks to the quality of content proposed to be published on the website. We expect more than 100 Contributors to be active during the project’s second year, when current community members will be incentivised to publish content more regularly (especially Early Adopters and TWGs moderators and regular members).

The **Moderator** is a member of the digiNEB.eu team that accesses the CMS of the web platform and can autonomously publish or edit content online. Currently, 9 people among consortium members are acting as moderators, while around 20 people are expected to play the active role of Moderator in the coming months of the project, possibly extending the role to initiatives formalising a synergy with digiNEB.eu.

The **Administrators** are a group of selected people among the Trust-IT + COMMpla team, i.e. the project partners responsible for the development of the digiNEB.eu website. This group of experienced people is responsible for assigning roles and responsibilities to each type of user profile and controls the type of content published online. Currently, 8 people are acting as Superusers on digiNEB.eu.

As of 30 June 2023, the five User Profiles are serving the number of users indicated in the table below. These quantities are constantly growing, with a final overall target of 2,000+ “validated/authenticated users” engaged by M24 (September 2024). From a technical perspective, such a target, together with the other project KPIs that are linked to the web platform, is amply compatible with the ICT infrastructure currently set-up and maintained by Trust-IT/COMMpla at www.digineb.eu (see also Sec. 5 “Website maintenance”).

Profile	Quantity	# of organisations
UP#1 - Anonymous visitor	About 12,000 (unique visitors from October 2022 to 15 July 2023)	N.A.
UP#2 - Community Member	57	50 organisations from 21 countries
UP#3 - Trusted contributor	6	6 organisations from 4 countries
UP#4 - Moderator	9	3 TU Delft, 2 EAAE, 2 ICF, 1 COMMpla, 1 InnovaWood
UP#5 - Administrator	7	5 Trust-IT, 2 COMMpla

Table 9 – Number of members in each User Profile (UP) as of June 2023

4.4 Website development, Personas and User Journeys

Considering this is a major website release, the Trust-IT and COMMpla dev team has followed a structured process to guarantee the best results, as sketched in the figure below. First, the marketing team provides a draft of the website structure and looks based on the main project goals, following UX design principles. The graphic team applies their experience to elaborate a visually attractive mockup, while the technical team is involved in the later implementation and testing phases, where the process goes back to the marketing team for feedback. In the mock-up phases, the tool FIGMA supports interactions between the various teams.

Figure 10 – Website internal process development

In addition to the process mentioned above, as the digiNEB.eu platform, in its Rel. 2.0 gradually increases its visibility with a wide range of stakeholders, it is crucial to understand their unique perspectives, needs, and aspirations. To facilitate effective communication and tailor the platform's offerings, seven distinct stakeholder “**personas**” have been developed, as per the figures below. Each

persona represents a specific stakeholder group, reflecting their diverse backgrounds, interests, and roles in shaping the future of Europe's built environment. By delving into these personas, it is possible to gain valuable insights into their motivations and expectations, allowing them to create meaningful experiences and foster fruitful collaborations within the digiNEB.eu community (for more details on this approach, see, for instance, the explanations by Gothelf and Seiden [/2/](#) and Knight [/3/](#)).

Sofia Morata

Senior Architect

(SG1 – Architects, Engineers Designers)

Age
40

Country
Spain

Highest level of education
Master University Degree in Architecture and Urban Planning

Work experience
10+Y

Awareness of NEB
High

Device
Desktop

Scenario for visiting the digiNEB.eu website

Sofia is an experienced architect from Spain. She is passionate about sustainable design and is looking for innovative digital solutions that align with the principles of the New European Bauhaus. Sofia wants to look for innovative digital solutions to incorporate into her daily workflow, explore success stories, join thematic working groups, and access training modules to enhance her skills in sustainable architecture.

Needs

- Access to innovative digital solutions for incorporating into daily workflow
- Exploration of success stories for inspiration and learning
- Participation in thematic working groups for collaboration and knowledge sharing
- Access to training modules for enhancing skills in sustainable architecture

Fears

- Missing out on the latest digital solutions and advancements in sustainable design
- Lack of inspiration and new ideas for incorporating sustainability into architectural projects
- Limited opportunities for collaboration and networking with like-minded professionals
- Insufficient skills and knowledge in sustainable architecture compared to industry standards

Source of visit

- visit prompted by researching a related topic - reads about trends in the news
- NEB-related pages
- Google organic search
- LinkedIn

Figure 11 – UX Persona for SG1

Lucas Schweinsteiger

CEO

(SG 2 - Industry Players)

Age
52

Country
Germany

Highest level of education
Master University Degree in Engineering

Work experience
20+Y

Awareness of NEB
Low

Device
Desktop - Mobile

Scenario for visiting the digiNEB.eu website

Lucas is a representative of an industrial company based in Germany. His company specialises in manufacturing sustainable building materials. Lucas visits digiNEB.eu to discover cutting-edge digital solutions that can be integrated into their production processes. He also wants to stay informed about policy developments and network with other industry players.

Needs

- Identification of cutting-edge digital solutions for integrating into their production processes
- Staying informed about policy developments related to sustainable building materials
- Networking with other industry players for collaboration and business opportunities

Fears

- Falling behind competitors in terms of adopting advanced digital solutions in manufacturing processes
- Missing out on policy updates that could impact their industry and business operations
- Limited networking opportunities leading to missed collaborations and potential growth

Source of visit

- visit prompted by researching industry innovations - reads about trends in the news
- Google organic search
- LinkedIn

Figure 12 – UX Persona for SG2

Maria Esposito

Postdoctoral Researcher (SG 3- Research and Academia)

Age
32

Country
Italy

Highest level of education
Doctoral University Degree in Arts and Innovation

Work experience
5+Y

Awareness of NEB
High

Device
Mobile + Desktop

Scenario for visiting the digiNEB.eu website

Maria is a researcher and academic from Italy. She focuses on sustainable urban planning and is interested in staying updated with the latest research findings and best practices. Maria uses digiNEB.eu as a resource to access research papers, join working groups, and collaborate with other researchers and academics across Europe.

Needs

- Staying updated with the latest research findings and best practices in sustainable urban planning
- Accessing research papers and scholarly resources related to the field
- Joining working groups and engaging in collaborations with other researchers and academics

Fears

- Missing out on important research findings and advancements in sustainable urban planning
- Limited access to relevant research papers and scholarly resources
- Lack of opportunities for collaboration and knowledge exchange with other researchers and academics

Source of visit

- visit prompted by researching a related topic - reads about trends in the news
- Google organic search
- LinkedIn

Figure 13 – UX Persona for SG3

Thomas Mertens

Web Designer & Developer (SG 4- Digital Technology Companies)

Age
35

Country
Belgium

Highest level of education
Bachelor University Degree in Computer Science

Work experience
10+Y

Awareness of NEB
Low

Device
Mobile + Desktop

Scenario for visiting the digiNEB.eu website

Thomas is a software developer from Belgium. He works for a digital technology company that specialises in creating innovative solutions for the construction industry. Thomas visits digiNEB.eu to showcase his company's digital tools, connect with potential clients, and collaborate with other experts in the field.

Needs

- Showcasing his company's digital tools and solutions to a relevant audience
- Connecting with potential clients and generating business opportunities
- Collaborating and exchanging ideas with other experts in the construction industry

Fears

- Lack of visibility and exposure for his company's digital tools
- Limited networking opportunities with potential clients and industry professionals
- Missed chances for collaboration and knowledge sharing in the field

Source of visit

- visit prompted by researching a related topic - reads about trends in the news
- Google organic search
- LinkedIn

Figure 14 – UX Persona for SG4

Emma Evra

Policymaker
(SG5 – Policy Makers)

Age
40

Country
France

Highest level of education
Master University Degree in International Relations

Work experience
15+Y

Awareness of NEB
Medium

Device
Mobile + Desktop

Scenario for visiting the digiNEB.eu website

Emma is a policy maker from France, working for a government agency focused on sustainable development. She visits digiNEB.eu to gather insights and ideas on sustainable design and construction practices. Emma aims to discover successful case studies and engage with stakeholders to shape policies that promote the New European Bauhaus principles.

Needs

- Gathering insights and ideas on sustainable design and construction practices
- Finding successful case studies for inspiration and learning
- Engaging with stakeholders to shape policies promoting the New European Bauhaus principles

Fears

- Lack of access to relevant information and resources on sustainable design and construction
- Difficulty in finding practical examples and case studies for policy development
- Limited engagement and collaboration with stakeholders in shaping sustainable development policies

Source of visit

- visit prompted by researching a related topic - reads about trends in the news
- European commission website
- Google organic search
- LinkedIn

Figure 15 – UX Persona for SG5

Erik Svensson

Policymaker
(SG6 – National & regional authorities)

Age
55

Country
Sweden

Highest level of education
Bachelor University Degree in Humanities

Work experience
25+Y

Awareness of NEB
Low

Device
Mobile + Desktop

Scenario for visiting the digiNEB.eu website

Erik is a representative of a regional authority in Sweden. He is responsible for urban planning and wants to incorporate sustainable design principles into local development projects. Erik visits digiNEB.eu to explore digital solutions to potentially implement, join thematic working groups to produce policy recommendations, and network with other regional authorities across Europe.

Needs

- Explore digital solutions for sustainable design implementation in local development projects
- Join thematic working groups to produce policy recommendations
- Network with other regional authorities across Europe

Fears

- Difficulty in finding suitable digital solutions for local development projects
- Limited resources or support for implementing sustainable design principles
- Ineffective collaboration or lack of engagement with other regional authorities

Source of visit

- visit prompted by researching a related topic - reads about trends in the news
- European commission website
- Google organic search
- LinkedIn

Figure 16 – UX Persona for SG6

Laura Jarvi

Policymaker
(SG7 - Civil society organisations)

Age
26

Country
Finland

Highest level of education
Bachelor University Degree in Political Sciences

Work experience
5-Y

Awareness of NEB
High

Device
Mobile + Desktop

Scenario for visiting the digiNEB.eu website

Laura is an environmental activist from Finland. She is passionate about citizen engagement and wants to contribute to the New European Bauhaus movement. Laura visits digiNEB.eu to access resources, attend online events, and connect with like-minded individuals and civil society organisations to drive positive change at the grassroots level.

Needs

- Access resources related to sustainable design and citizen engagement
- Attend online events to stay informed about the New European Bauhaus movement
- Connect with like-minded individuals and civil society organisations

Fears

- Limited access to relevant resources and information
- Ineffective communication channels for connecting with other activists and organisations
- Insufficient opportunities for meaningful involvement and impact

Source of visit

- visit prompted by researching a related topic - reads about trends in the news
- European commission website
- Google organic search
- LinkedIn

Figure 17 – UX Persona for SG7

As mentioned, the personas outlined above represent the diverse **stakeholder groups** that form the foundation of the digiNEB.eu platform dedicated to creating a digital ecosystem for different stakeholder groups acting in the context of the New European Bauhaus. By recognising and understanding the unique perspectives of architects, designers, engineers, industry players, researchers, policy makers, national and regional authorities, and civil society organisations, it is possible to create a UX that adds unique value to each stakeholder group while providing them with seamlessly navigation tools and a user-friendly platform allowing multiple stakeholder groups to share knowledge and best practices.

Moreover, through its user-friendly features, the platform also allows to create a networking space to create synergies among different stakeholder groups. Such an aim explicitly fosters the NEB values of co-creation and collaboration. Through the many assets provided by the digiNEB.eu's platform – e.g., observatory of success stories, thematic working groups, e-Learning platform, and other resources – different stakeholder groups can come together to share knowledge, exchange ideas, and co-create innovative solutions. Moreover, by capturing their expertise, experiences, and aspirations, the digiNEB.eu can create a digital platform to collect and share best practices, ideas and know-how, creating a co-creation space that aligns with the goals of the New European Bauhaus.

4.5 Wireflows and wireframes

As part of the web platform's design and development process of Release 2.0, several wireflows and wireframes have been developed. Samples are represented in the figures below. The initial requirements have been translated into key concepts to be displayed on the website. The website's homepage has been updated to reflect progress in the platform's sections and modules.

Figure 18 – Updated homepage hero with video

Figure 19 – Updated NEB digital ecosystem section on the homepage

Figure 20 – Interactive timeline on the homepage

Thematic Working Groups

The Thematic Working Groups (TWGs) bring together top-class experts of the NEB digital ecosystem to stimulate discussions and share best practices that are collected to provide strategic policy recommendations. digiNEB.eu foresees the following 4 main TWGs to bring these discussions forward.

Design and Architecture

Focused on enhancing biodiversity with eco-systemic decision-making in design, morphology of human settlements; architectural-data cycles for sustainable design qualities and more

Production and Construction

Focused on digitising the building sector, data sharing and data management, technologies for a sustainable construction industry and more!

Verticals

Focused on healthy living environment and buildings for healthcare, education, future-proof heritage and more!

Community and Sustainability

Focused on user-centred criteria and participatory design processes for sustainable and smart urbanisation, equity and empowerment for disenfranchised populations and more!

JOIN THE THEMATIC WORKING GROUPS NOW! →

Figure 21 – Thematic Working Groups (TWGs) homepage section with CTA

Figure 22 – Early Adopters homepage section with CTA

Figure 23 – Updated news and events homepage section with CTA

Moreover, different assets have been added on separate pages. As part of the adopted workflow sketched in Figure 10, “Website internal process development”, the wireframe has been developed in order to start the building of the website, defining the communication message that has been present on the home page. When the concept has been validated and revised, a mockup has been produced where the key message present in the wireframe has been translated into UI. Some sample pages that have undergone this process are shown below.

Figure 24 – Website mock-up (early adopters page - first draft)

digiNEB.eu ABOUT ▾ PLATFORM ▾ TWGS EARLY ADOPTERS NEWS & EVENTS ▾ EAG Log in Get engaged →

Early Adopters of digital solutions in the NEB context

digiNEB.eu Early Adopters have direct experience using digital tools aligned with the New European Bauhaus (NEB) principles.

What do Early Adopters bring to NEB?

Their direct experience in NEB-related projects, in all domains, from concept, planning, design, construction, decommissioning, and more.

What's in it for you?

Why become an Early Adopter – Early Adopters gain visibility, both at the local and European level, in several ways. They will be joining webinars and workshops where they can showcase their best practices and act in their local community to spread the values and opportunities brought by NEB.

Would you like to become an Early Adopter? Fill in the form below

Our Early Adopters

<p>Sandra Vengadasalam Initiator and Co-Founder blaxberg Blockchain Bloxberg</p>		
<p>Mercedes Rois Director XERA Axencia Galega da Industria Forestal</p>		

Figure 25 – Website mock-up (early adopters page - final release)

Figure 26 – Website mock-up (eLearning platform - first draft)

Figure 27 – Mock-up of the eLearning catalogue

4.6 External users' contribution

To facilitate external contributions, digiNEB.eu provides a dedicated dashboard designed for contributors. Within this interface, contributors have the capability to add, edit, and submit their content for review. However, content publication remains the sole prerogative of website UPs with review and approval rights for publication, as indicated in Sec. 4.3 “Website privileges and User Profiles (UPs)”.

Content Types:

Digital Toolkit: external contributors are encouraged to contribute to the digiNEB.eu Digital Toolkit comprising resources, guides, and tools related to digital transformation. By leveraging the dashboard, contributors can propose valuable additions, edits, or new content to enhance the Toolkit's value for the digiNEB.eu community.

Success Story: external contributors can share their success stories with the digiNEB.eu community, highlighting their accomplishments and insights gained. The UI interface allows users to easily compile a factsheet, provide a textual account and add relevant infographics.

eLearning section: users can reach out to the digiNEB.eu team to upload their training modules to the digiNEB.eu online catalogue linking them to external platforms. In release 2.1, they will also be enabled to share external training material autonomously by creating an account on the platform. This will allow for seamless integration of existing training resources, maximising accessibility and diversity.

By reaching out to the digiNEB.eu team, users can also personalise their training modules using the digiNEB.eu customised eLearning environment powered by the cost-free TRUST-LCMS product. This integration with digiNEB.eu offers a tailored and interactive learning experience within the digiNEB.eu platform. Both external and original digiNEB.eu courses will feature in the “Training” catalogue, fully accessible after free registration to the platform.

This feature is provided by different community modules, commonly used in the Drupal community and regularly maintained. They have to be configured and set following the logic necessary to implement.

In Drupal 9, Workbench and Workflow are powerful modules that enable non-administrator/editor users to contribute content to a website. Let's take a closer look at these modules and how they facilitate content contribution.

Workbench:

Workbench is a suite of modules in Drupal that provides a unified interface for managing content. It introduces a hierarchical structure that allows different user roles to work on specific website sections. Here's how Workbench enables content contribution:

Workbench Access: This module allows administrators to define editorial access control and assign specific site sections to different user roles. For example, you can assign a specific user role the ability to contribute content to a particular section or subsection of the website.

Workbench Moderation: This module adds a moderation workflow to content editing. It enables content to go through various stages (e.g., draft, needs review, published) before publishing on the live site. Non-administrator/editor users can create content and submit it for review, while the editorial team can review, approve, or request revisions before publishing.

Workflow:

Workflow is another module in Drupal that provides a flexible content publishing process. It allows administrators to define custom workflows for different content types. Here's how Workflow facilitates content contribution:

Content Type Workflows: With Workflow, administrators can define specific workflows for each content type. For instance, you can create a workflow with steps like content creation, review, and publication. Non-administrator/editor users can create content and submit it for review, following the defined workflow.

Transition States: Workflow enables administrators to define different states or stages that content can go through. Each state can have associated permissions, such as who can create, edit, or review content in that state. This allows non-administrator/editor users to participate in the content contribution process within their assigned roles and permissions.

By combining the functionalities of Workbench and Workflow, Drupal 9 empowers non-administrator/editor users to contribute content to a website. They can create, edit, and submit content for review, while administrators and editorial teams can manage the approval process and ensure quality before publishing the content live. These modules offer a robust system for collaborative content creation and enable a more inclusive content contribution experience in Drupal.

Below are some examples of the digiNEB.eu user interface (UI) for external contributors.

Figure 28 – digiNEB.eu UI dashboard (platform back-end)

Figure 29 – Defined steps in the editorial workflow

LABEL	FROM	TO	
+ <td>Create New Draft</td> <td>Draft</td> <td>Draft</td>	Create New Draft	Draft	Draft
+ <td>Send to review</td> <td>Draft</td> <td>In review</td>	Send to review	Draft	In review
+ <td>Send to draft</td> <td>In review</td> <td>Draft</td>	Send to draft	In review	Draft
+ <td>Publish now</td> <td>Draft, In review, Published</td> <td>Published</td>	Publish now	Draft, In review, Published	Published
+ <td>Archive</td> <td>Published</td> <td>Archived</td>	Archive	Published	Archived
+ <td>Restore to Draft</td> <td>Archived</td> <td>Draft</td>	Restore to Draft	Archived	Draft
+ <td>Restore</td> <td>Archived</td> <td>Published</td>	Restore	Archived	Published
+ <td>Publish to draft</td> <td>Published</td> <td>Draft</td>	Publish to draft	Published	Draft

Figure 30 – Defined transitions in the editorial workflow

5. Website maintenance

This section presents updates to the website development provided in D2.1, especially in terms of its analytical data collection and monitoring system in place.

5.1 Maintenance team

The website is maintained by the Trust-IT+COMMpla tech team. They routinely perform the following tasks:

- Hosting management;
- Technical maintenance;
- Monitoring.

The maintenance team is also responsible for designing and implementing all further evolutions of the web platform. Minor releases (e.g., 1.1, 1.2) have been performed, adding new functionalities and/or sections.

5.2 Hosting

Trust-IT hosts the website on its virtual servers in **AWS** (Amazon Web Services). AWS guarantees the servers to be in the Ireland region to maintain all the data in the European Union (with Respect to GDPR, see also D1.2 “Data management plan”).

The service used to host the website is **EC2 (Elastic Compute)** able to virtualise a server and use it as a single point of development. This approach is quite spread in deployment guidelines to isolate an environment and base it on the current bare metal capabilities. AWS ensures excellent service to avoid any type of physical accident, disaster recovery, etc. Lastly, the deployment is completely agnostic in terms of availability of resources, physical maintenance, and any other aspect to be considered in a typical server farm.

The platform monitoring is provided by UptimeRobot, which periodically checks if the website replies to the tool request and sends a notification to all technical department communication channels to put in place a mitigation/resolution plan to resolve the inconvenience.

To further minimise the risk of technical failures leading to website unavailability, all the AWS best practices have been followed to have a reliable and resilient environment. The latest platform availability data (as of 20 July 2023) indicate an **uptime of 99.314% since January 1st 2023**, which, considering the intense and frequent development sessions that the web platform has been undergoing in the past weeks and months, is quite remarkable (less than 34 hours in the past 201 days). We expect this performance to be kept at these levels in the upcoming months.

5.3 Data analytics and KPI monitoring

As envisioned in D2.1, a customised dashboard has been set up on **Looker Studio**, whose main input is regularly updated through **Google Analytics** data sources. In this way, detailed statistics on website visitors and users have been derived.

While the project’s **KPIs monitoring** as a whole falls under the responsibility of T4.3, “Impact monitoring, benchmarking, and user feedback,” the digiNEB.eu Looker Studio account serves the purpose of setting the monitoring mechanisms needed to track the project KPIs related to website performance, proactively detect possible problems, and implement corrective actions.

The Google Analytics profile has been operative since October 2022, and the first data about visitors' clicks on calls to action and conversions are being tracked. Significant datasets are already present in this version; updates are disclosed in the upcoming deliverables and project update reports. Below is a screenshot of the digiNEB.eu dashboard containing data records from October 2022 to mid-June 2023.

Figure 31 – digiNEB.eu Looker Studio Dashboard from October 1st 2022 to June 15 2023

5.4 Platform Monitoring

As for the platform monitoring, the website and database instances complete the digiNEB.eu solution is still monitored automatically using Uptime Robot (uptimerobot.com), a free service to monitor if the website or any other endpoint is up. In case of failure, the system sends an email to flag the problem. The notification is sent via email to the Technical team of Trust-IT and via other channels (Internal Technical Communication Channel, private Smartphone of key technical employees of Trust-IT) exploiting 3rd party webhooks.

6. Terms of use, data management, and ethics

Concerning terms of use, data management, and ethics of Rel. 2.0 of the digiNEB.eu web platform, an independent, specialised firm, has been consulted ([ICT Legal Consulting](#)), and their input has been implemented, leading to a revised version of both terms of use and privacy statements adopted by www.digineb.eu. The revised approach is described in the sections below. Further details are included in D1.3 “Ethics Report, Year 1”.

6.1 Background

Complying with the Grant Agreement /1/, the digiNEB.eu Consortium is fully aware of and respects Digital Europe's ethical rules and standards and those reflected in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and the Data Protection Directive (Directive 95/46/EC). Be that as it may, complying with the GA, the Consortium has sought assistance, in Month 9, from an external advisor, *ICT Legal Consulting* and their team of lawyers, specialised in European New Technologies Law, led by Paolo Balboni (Professor of Privacy, Cybersecurity, and IT Contract Law at the European Centre on Privacy and Cybersecurity – ECPC, Faculty of Law Maastricht University). The Ethics Advisor thoroughly self-assessed the project regarding data management, privacy, and ethics at large and provided insights to update digiNEB.eu's posture in those areas.

Following ICT Legal's consultancy, copyright and intellectual property issues related to content presented by the website were revised (see the updated website's terms of use [here](#)) to ensure compliance with **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International licence (CC BY 4.0)**. Other specific aspects of the digital processes implemented on the digiNEB.eu web platforms, particularly linked to the involvement of external users, events management, data retention and personal data retention, have also been addressed and will be reported in D1.3 “Ethics Report” to be delivered in Month 12 of the project (September 2023).

6.2 Terms of use for the digital solutions published in the Digital Hub

To provide the desired, open & collaborative approach to the Digital Toolkit, Observatory, and Training sections of the web platform, the website's terms of use have been updated as part of Rel. 2.0 (see [here](#)). These datasets of online catalogues, digital solutions, success stories and training materials are provided to website users “AS IS” and “AS AVAILABLE”. Thus, the digiNEB.eu consortium is not responsible for the quality of each digital solution published in the Digital Hub, for which each digital provider retains all rights and obligations towards the end-users. As such, the digiNEB.eu consortium expressly disclaims all warranties, whether express, implied, statutory or otherwise, with respect to the service provided by digiNEB.eu Hub, including all implied warranties of merchantability, fitness for a particular purpose, title and non-infringement, and warranties that may arise out of the course of dealing, course of performance, usage or trade practice.

6.3 Privacy

The website complies with the GDPR (Directive 95/46/EC). The approach followed by digiNEB.eu in managing personal data reduces the collection and retention of personal data to the absolute minimum. Any data or information collected are held private and strictly confidential. Moreover, data obtained incidentally within the project are handled with confidentiality and managed according to the GDPR /4/.

Processing for this purpose is generally necessary to allow the DATA CONTROLLER Team to respond to any request to register to the platform/newsletter or sign up for an event/webinar. Therefore, it is necessary for the performance of a contract – Art. 6(1)(b) GDPR. Trust-IT srl, as identified at the top of this Privacy Policy, is the data controller regarding all personal data processing carried out through the Website. Any questions related to this Privacy Policy or the Trust-IT Services' data processing practices can be directed to the firm through written communication to privacy@digneb.eu or via the contact forms available on the Website.

However, the tracking of website/newsletter registrants, event attendance and publication of attendee lists is done on the basis of the Website's interests in managing subscribers and events and allowing other participants to become aware of the community – Art. 6(1)(f) GDPR.

In any case, data acquired via the web portal or during event registration shall never be used for commercial purposes or shared with any third parties not identified in the [Privacy Policy](#), in compliance with the "purpose limitation" principle according to which personal data shall be collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes – Art. 5(1)(b), GDPR. Lastly, the terms of use of the website are published [here](#).

6.4 Copyright, Intellectual Property, Liability

digiNEB.eu provides users with access to a range of content types, including the Digital Toolkit, Success Stories, eLearning Courses, and research results. The Consortium acknowledges that third parties retain ownership rights to the materials they contribute, and DigiNEB.eu reproduces, displays, and makes them available on the website for research and dissemination purposes. Any use of third-party material requires explicit agreement with the respective owner.

The content on the website is intended for general information purposes. While DigiNEB.eu strives to ensure the accuracy and completeness of the materials, including user-contributed content like Success Stories and Thematic Working Groups (TWGs), no representations or warranties are made regarding their accuracy or completeness.

As digiNEB.eu includes links to third-party websites, it is important to note that digiNEB.eu has no control over the nature and content of those websites. The use of such websites is governed by the specific terms set by their owners, and DigiNEB.eu accepts no liability for any loss or damage arising from their use. As such, digiNEB.eu does not assume responsibility or liability for any damages or losses arising from, or in connection with, the use of its website or the materials displayed on it. It is important for users to exercise their judgement and discretion when utilising the website and its content.

digiNEB.eu is committed to continuously improving its communication and reserves the right to make further improvements or changes to the online content without prior notice.

6.5 Involvement of external users

The registration process for the digiNEB.eu Project website is carried out through a dedicated form called "Create a new account - Join our Community," accessible at <https://digneb.eu/user/register>. This form requires individuals interested in registering on the portal to provide certain information, including their email address, name and surname, a self-description, and a profile picture. The form also includes checkboxes for subscribing to the Project newsletter and acknowledging the Terms of Use and Privacy Policy. Feedback regarding the registration form has been collected and is outlined below.

Personal information is provided spontaneously by the user with explicit consent and subscription to data processing policies during the registration phase. In order to ensure the website's overall compliance with EU GDPR, a clear-cut division between mandatory and optional fields was established.

Mandatory fields

- "Email address": the email field is mandatory for registration and is used for system communication and notifications. The email address provided is not made public and is solely used for specific purposes related to the individual's preferences.
- "Name and Surname": providing the name and surname is mandatory for registration and serves the purpose of personal identification within the platform.
- Checkbox for acknowledging the Terms of Use and Privacy Policy: users must acknowledge both the Terms of Use and Privacy Policy to reflect an acknowledgement of having read and understood the Privacy Policy rather than seeking explicit acceptance.

Optional fields

- "What describes you best?": this field offers a drop-down menu with several options for individuals to select. If "other" is chosen, individuals are prompted to specify their self-description in a free text field. Since free text fields carry the risk of collecting unnecessary or sensitive information, the field was made optional, and a disclaimer with clear instructions on the type of information required was provided as a risk mitigation measure.
- "Tell us something about you": being a free text field, this field may pose data protection concerns as personal information could be collected. To address these concerns, a disclaimer with clear instructions was provided to guide registrants on the type of information expected and to discourage sharing special categories of personal data.
- Checkbox to subscribe to the newsletter: this field is optional, and in light of data protection regulations, a disclaimer linked to the registration to the newsletter was added. Concerning the third-party technical provider (a "data processor" clearly indicated in digiNEB's privacy statement here), a migration from Mailchimp to Mailjet was carried out, considering the better quality-to-price ratio of the services and improved GDPR compliance and user data transparency.

6.6 Data gathered at events

Enrolment to events organised by digiNEB.eu is currently being carried out primarily via the website. The Zoom event sign-up form includes mandatory and optional fields, which have been modified and improved to make them more compliant with website users' GDPR. Here is feedback on the main fields included in the registration forms:

Mandatory fields

- "Name," "Surname," and Email address: these fields are mandatory for individuals to register for the event. The provided personal data is processed according to the outlined GDPR-compliant principles.
- Checkbox for acknowledging the Terms of Use and Privacy Policy: users are required to acknowledge both the Terms of Use and Privacy Policy to reflect an acknowledgement of having read and understood the Privacy Policy rather than seeking explicit acceptance.

Optional fields

- "What describes you best?": this field offers a drop-down menu with several options for individuals to select. If "other" is chosen, individuals are prompted to specify their self-

description in a free text field. The field was made optional since free text fields risk collecting unnecessary or sensitive information. A disclaimer with clear instructions on the type of information required was provided as a risk mitigation measure.

- “How did you hear about this webinar?”: being a free text field, this field may pose data protection concerns as personal information could be collected. To address these concerns, a disclaimer with clear instructions was provided to guide registrants on the type of information expected and to discourage sharing special categories of personal data.
- This field is optional, and in light of data protection regulations, a disclaimer linked to the registration to the newsletter was added. Concerning the third-party technical provider (a “data processor” clearly indicated in digiNEB’s privacy statement here), a migration from Mailchimp to Mailjet was carried out, considering the services' better quality-to-price ratio and improved GDPR compliance and users’ data transparency.

6.7 Retention period of personal data

The collected data will be kept for a period not exceeding the achievement of the purposes for which they are processed ("conservation limitation principle", art.5, GDPR) or for the time necessary for the obligations of law and EC-funded projects Rules.

The verification of the obsolescence of the data stored in relation to the purposes for which it was collected is carried out periodically, and obsolete data are erased permanently from the website database.

6.8 Content management

As of Rel. 2.0 official release, three platform sections pose potential legal concerns: Digital Toolkit, Success Stories, and eLearning Platform. The Digital Tool Kit comprises information sheets presenting software and applications useful to the industry. These sheets are generated in three ways: partners create them, developers upload their own sheets, or developers independently upload sheets. Two scenarios should be considered: partners autonomously create the content, or developers upload the content before registration. For copyright protection, authorisation is required for using protected images and materials, while hyperlinking is generally permissible unless the linked content is known to be illegal. To mitigate copyright infringement risks, the project will seek authorisation by contacting solutions providers and requesting written consent to publish their solutions. In scenario 2, the project will ensure users have the right to upload content, establish licensing agreements, and define content restrictions. Data protection principles will also be considered, and the privacy policy will be updated accordingly. The Success Stories section showcases industry solutions and can be written by partners or the Project community. Similar copyright considerations as in the Digital Toolkit apply, and contact with relevant projects will be established to ensure compliance with agreements and permissions for using protected material. User-generated content will be subjected to the same authorisation. Additionally, from an ethical and data protection perspective, should any individuals’ personal data be published, they will be informed and given the opportunity to provide consent.

The e-learning platform offers courses hosted externally or internally. For externally hosted courses, specific agreements will arise to regulate content display and usage, seeking authorisation and complying with third-party terms. Internally hosted courses will be categorised into scenarios. Scenario 1 involves content developed by the project, necessitating agreements with users to regulate licensing and platform usage. Scenario 2 involves content developed by partners or external parties, requiring agreements to obtain permissions, define licensing terms, and facilitate content distribution. As work by digiNEB.eu’s Ethical Board progresses, the website's Terms of Use will be amended to address these aspects.

7. Future Steps

7.1 Adjustments to privacy & terms of use

Following the recommendations gathered during the interim project review, the digiNEB.eu privacy policy was amended as described in D1.3. As a consequence, the Trust-IT/COMMpla team implemented two main changes to its privacy policy and terms of use to enhance its structure and align with GDPR compliance, based on feedback from the interim review meeting held on December 6, 2023:

- 1. Modification in Privacy Policy - Section 3 “Purposes of Processing”:** the reference to processing registrants' payment details for events and webinars was initially included to cover potential event fees. This change was made as no events requiring payment were held in the first 14 months of the project. Should any fee-based events be organised in the future, the consortium will need to update the privacy policy accordingly to reflect this.
- 2. Modification in Terms of Use - Section 2 “Copyright / Intellectual Property”:** the terms of use were revised to make the policy more user-friendly and to encourage the use of materials published on the site. The original text, which required explicit agreement for the use of third-party material, was modified to clarify that general use of materials, as presented on the website, is allowed without additional permissions. Specific or personalised uses of third-party content require contacting the respective providers. The revised text maintains the essence of the original while providing clearer guidelines for users.

These updates reflect the digiNEB.eu platform's commitment to continuous improvement in communication and adherence to GDPR standards ensures a more user-friendly and compliant user experience.

7.2 Handover of the platform from Trust-IT and COMMpla to TU DELFT

The handover process for the digiNEB.eu platform, managed by the Trust-IT/COMMpla team, involves several key steps to ensure a smooth transition to TU Delft, the beneficiary, and the rest of the consortium's partners. This includes the removal of unnecessary admin accounts, leaving only one profile whose credentials will be transferred to TU Delft. The GDPR consent management, currently handled by a custom Drupal module developed by Trust-IT Services, will also be transferred, requiring the endpoint to be changed to a backend managed by TU Delft.

Additionally, the entire website filesystem will be zipped and sent to TU Delft, including the Drupal CMS and static files for CMS configuration, assets, and templates. The same process applies to the Flarum instance used for the Thematic Working Groups (TWGs) forum and the Moodle LMS for the e-learning platform, encompassing both filesystems and database dumps.

This multistep handover will ensure that TU Delft will be able to retain full control and management capabilities over the digiNEB.eu platform, including its external components (e.g. TWG forums and e-learning platform). This transition aligns with the agreed terms within the consortium and is designed to maintain the platform's integrity and effectiveness while facilitating future developments and enhancements of the platform under TU Delft's stewardship in conformity with the digiNEB.eu project's future results. Below is a list of the main handover tasks:

Digineb.eu item	Handover details	Beneficiary
Removal of unnecessary admin accounts	All the unnecessary accounts with Administrator role. Only 1 profile will be present and the credential will be sent to the beneficiary	TU DELFT
GDPR consents management	Currently the GDPR consents are collected using a Drupal custom module developed by Trust-IT Services. The custom module will be present in the website filesystem described below. The custom module sends consents to a centralised server owned by Trust-IT Services. The endpoint has to be changed to a beneficiary backend able to manage the endpoint.	TU DELFT
Website filesystem	The Drupal CMS uses static files to manage CMS configuration, assets, template definition, etc. All the current document root will be zipped and send to the beneficiary	TU DELFT
Website database	The website database dump will be sent to the beneficiary in order to restore it in a fresh instance	TU DELFT
TWG forum filesystem	The Flarum instance use static files to manage the configuration, assets, template definition, etc. All the current document root will be zipped and sent to the beneficiary	TU DELFT
TWG forum database	The Flarum database dump will be sent to the beneficiary in order to restore it in a fresh instance	TU DELFT
eLearning platform filesystem	The Moodle LMS uses static files to manage LMS configuration, assets, template definition, etc. All the current document root will be zipped and sent to the beneficiary	TU DELFT
eLearning platform database	The Moodle database dump will be sent to the beneficiary in order to restore it in a fresh instance	TU DELFT

Table 10. digiNEB.eu platform handover details

8. Conclusions

This deliverable describes the current status of the digiNEB.eu web platform, available at www.digineb.eu, emphasising the main transformations progressively delivered between the first release (Rel. 1.0) of October 2022 and this second one (Rel. 2.0) of June 2023.

Building on Rel. 1.0 and its subsequent minor releases (1.1, 1.2, and 1.3), Rel. 2.0 has been developed in Drupal 9, following state-of-the-art web criteria, following UI/UX design principles, and utilising computing resources on a public cloud with servers in Europe. digiNEB.eu is maintained by the Trust-IT/COMMpla technical team, continuously monitoring performances, gathering user feedback, and performing regular SEO activities.

The various functionalities offered to the end-users have constantly evolved in the first nine months of the project, collecting feedback from various sources (including internal queries from the partners, an anonymous public survey, and an external user UX workshop). The platform content and functionalities are utilised in the dissemination and engagement effort towards the target audience, in agreement with the project plans and GA and translating them into “assets” of digiNEB.eu, currently being leveraged to achieve the project’s goals and create impact. This represents a strong vantage point for digiNEB.eu, in that, without any delay in the timeline of the project, all the tools and macro-functionalities indicated in the Grant Agreement have been timely delivered, and the Consortium will be able to direct their resources in populating the platform with the rich content and opportunities envisaged to achieve the level of engagement of the community indicated by the Grant Agreement and the subsequent project deliverables, particularly D4.1 “Stakeholder engagement plan and adoption & monitoring report – initial version”, and D5.1 “Plan for dissemination, exploitation, communication activities (DECP)”.

Concerning terms of use, data management, and ethics of Rel. 2.0 of the digiNEB.eu web platform, an independent, specialised firm, has been consulted ([ICT Legal Consulting](#)), and their input has been implemented, leading to a revised version of both terms of use and privacy statements adopted by www.digineb.eu. For content, adoption of the CC BY 4.0 licence has been expressly indicated, and other input has been given to revise processes concerning data management and privacy. In particular, matters such as data retention, events management, IP, copyright and privacy have been addressed and amendments made to improve the project’s overall compliance and best practices.

Further changes to the platform's Privacy Policy and Terms of Use have also been implemented following the recommendations received at the project's Interim Review on December 2023.

A third and final release of the digiNEB.eu website (Rel. 3.0) will be delivered in M18 (March 2024, as D2.3 “digiNEB.eu web platform, Rel. 3.0”), taking stock of the feedback of the user base, proactively evolving the technical assets of the web platform, and further aligning the website with the NEB digital ecosystem. This new release will be handled by consortium partner TU Delft, to whom the Trust-IT/COMMpla team will hand over the platform as described in Sec. [7.2](#).

9. References

/1/ digiNEB.eu Grant Agreement, DIGITAL-CSA number 101083743, funded under the Digital Europe Programme (October 2022).

/2/ Gothelf, J. and Seiden J. *Lean UX: Designing Great Products with Agile Teams*. Sebastopol CA: O'Reilly Media, 2016

/3/ Knight, W. *UX for Developers: How to Integrate User-Centered Design Principles Into your Day-to-Day Development Work*. Northampton: Apress, 2019.

/4/ [General Data Protection Regulation](#) (GDPR), Regulation EU 2016/679.

Appendix A

Rolling Excel sheet containing comments from the digiNEB.eu Consortium, from February through May 2023.

#	Section	Issue	Insertion date	Inserted by	Frontend / Backend	Status	Resolution date	Notes
1	Digital Toolkit	Make image-logo name-giving automatic	21/02/2023	EAAE	Backend	Blocked		Not possible for SEO reasons
2	Digital Toolkit	Remove payoff field	21/02/2023	EAAE	Backend	Done	22/02/2023	
3	Digital Toolkit	Better explain what body is	21/02/2023	EAAE	Backend	Done	22/02/2023	
4	Digital Toolkit	Remove Html text format	21/02/2023	EAAE	Backend	Done	22/02/2023	
5	Digital Toolkit	General data (e.g. link to solution/contacts on top)	21/02/2023	EAAE	Backend	Done	22/02/2023	
6	Digital Toolkit	Reorder: link to solution/provider name/provider contact/provider website (place it at the beginning of the factsheet)	21/02/2023	EAAE	Backend	Done	22/02/2023	
7	Digital Toolkit	Autoflatten text (if possible)	21/02/2023	EAAE	Backend	Blocked		Not possible
8	Digital Toolkit	Explain fields What is it - Who is this for	21/02/2023	EAAE	Backend	Done	22/02/2023	

#	Section	Issue	Insertion date	Inserted by	Frontend / Backend	Status	Resolution date	Notes
9	Digital Toolkit	Stakeholder group (up to three choices)	21/02/2023	EAAE	Backend	Done	22/02/2023	
10	Digital Toolkit	Insert New field: NEB prize	21/02/2023	EAAE	Backend	Done	23/02/2023	
11	Digital Toolkit	Insert field NEB value	21/02/2023	EAAE	Backend	Done	23/02/2023	
12	Success Stories	Change body/footer/specs	21/02/2023	EAAE	Backend	Done	22/02/2023	
13	Success Stories	Success story: Image selection just upload, remove library	21/02/2023	EAAE	Backend	Done	05/05/2023	
14	Website UI/UX	Provide preview and edit functionality for the content that is added by partners, champions and others	21/02/2023	TU DELFT	Backend	Done	11/05/2023	
15	Digital Toolkit	Fix flipping cards	21/02/2023	TU DELFT	Frontend	Done	05/05/2023	
16	Website UI/UX	Adjust anchor leading to Early Adopters	21/02/2023	TU DELFT	Frontend	Done	22/02/2023	
17	Website Homepage	Early Adopters (shorten form, remove keywords field)	21/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Frontend	Done	18/04/2023	
18	Website UI/UX	Fix anchor for TWG	21/02/2023	TU DELFT	Frontend	Done	22/02/2023	

#	Section	Issue	Insertion date	Inserted by	Frontend / Backend	Status	Resolution date	Notes
19	Digital Toolkit	Allow users to modify published content	21/02/2023	EAAE	Backend	Done	11/05/2023	
20	Success Stories	Allow users to modify published content	21/02/2023	EAAE	Backend	Done	11/05/2023	
21	Early Adopters	Allow users to modify published content	21/02/2023	EAAE	Backend	Done	11/05/2023	
22	Website Homepage	Modify the partners page and how the content is showcased (use the same animation of the Toolkit)	21/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Frontend	Done	23/02/2023	
23	Digital Toolkit	Make solution of the month editable by admin	21/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Backend	Done	22/02/2023	
24	Digital Toolkit	Find new animation for mobile version (alternative to flipping cards)	21/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Frontend	Done	05/05/2023	
25	TWG	CTA linked to the discussions	21/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Frontend	Done	23/02/2023	
26	Digital Toolkit	Make the pages linked to each other	21/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Frontend	Done	05/05/2023	
27	Success Stories	Make the pages linked to each other	21/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Frontend	Done	05/05/2023	
28	Website Homepage	Link TWG with What's new in the observatory	21/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Frontend	Done	05/05/2023	
29	News	Make image + text clickable	21/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Frontend	Done	22/02/2023	

#	Section	Issue	Insertion date	Inserted by	Frontend / Backend	Status	Resolution date	Notes
30	EAG	Add the bio of each EAG	21/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Frontend	Done	23/02/2023	
31	EAG	All page clickable (not only the name)	21/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Frontend	Done	22/02/2023	
32	EAG	LinkedIn to be placed under the bio	21/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Frontend	Done	22/02/2023	
33	Website Homepage	Redo the NEB image close to the main payoff (similar to the NEB image)	21/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Frontend	Done	05/05/2023	
34	Website Homepage	Take out flipping stakeholder cards from the HP and create an internal page	21/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Frontend	Done	23/02/2023	
35	Website Homepage	Change the green colour of the text	21/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Frontend	Done	05/05/2023	
36	Digital Toolkit	Make * as a mandatory field	21/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Backend	Done	05/05/2023	
37	Digital Toolkit	Provider etc to be placed in the upper side	21/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Backend	Done	05/05/2023	
38	Website Homepage	Solution Contacts to be moved as Provider Contact (email)	21/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Backend	Done	22/02/2023	
39	Digital Toolkit	Who is it for - to be transformed as a dropdown	21/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Backend	Blocked		Drop down menu already present
40	Success Stories	Substitute Green dimension to NEB values	21/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Backend	Done	22/02/2023	

#	Section	Issue	Insertion date	Inserted by	Frontend / Backend	Status	Resolution date	Notes
41	Digital Toolkit	Create sections for the fields adding a content	22/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Backend	Done	22/02/2023	
42	Success Stories	Remove Revision log from	22/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Backend	Done	22/02/2023	
43	Early Adopters	Remove Revision log from	22/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Backend	Done	22/02/2023	
44	Success Stories	Move comments below and hide some fields	22/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Backend	Done	23/02/2023	
45	Digital Toolkit	Describe label for summary. put placeholder in description	22/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Backend	Done	22/02/2023	
46	Website Homepage	Specific page for the Home Page section "digiNEB.eu delivers value for:"	22/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Frontend	Done	23/02/2023	
47	Website Homepage	Remove block "digiNEB.eu delivers value for"	22/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Frontend	Done	23/02/2023	
48	Website Homepage	Link from single page to anchor of HP	22/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Frontend	In progress		
49	TWG	Modify the graphic of the TWG discussion groups	22/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Frontend	Blocked		More discussions within the consortium are needed
50	Digital	Add "main technology" as additional filter in the digital	23/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Backend	Done	05/05/2023	

#	Section	Issue	Insertion date	Inserted by	Frontend / Backend	Status	Resolution date	Notes
	Toolkit	toolkit and success stories						
51	Success Stories	Add "main technology" as additional filter in the digital toolkit and success stories	23/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Backend	Done	05/05/2023	
52	Digital Toolkit	Add TWG relation	23/02/2023	TRUST-IT	Backend	Done	05/05/2023	
53	Digital Toolkit	Send email to solution owner about publication with link to revise information	23/02/2023	EAAE	Backend	To discuss further		A best-practice procedure will be agreed
54	Digital Toolkit	Give NEB values options (people do not need to know which values there are)	23/02/2023	EAAE	Backend	Blocked		Values need to be better defined within consortium
55	Success Stories	Put a title in the menu for "Success stories" and link to a page to be created that shows only this type of content	07/04/2023	TRUST-IT	Frontend	Done	11/05/2023	
56	Digital Toolkit	Make number likes and comments on the digital toolkit and observatory items visible	07/04/2023	TRUST-IT	Frontend	Done	05/05/2023	
57	Observatory	Make number likes and comments on the digital toolkit and observatory items visible	07/04/2023	TRUST-IT	Frontend	Done	05/05/2023	
58	Website Homepage	Make Navigation Bar more user friendly (what is a TWG an EAG? Are these important for users?) Rethink categories	28/04/2023	EAAE	Frontend	Done	20/06/2023	

#	Section	Issue	Insertion date	Inserted by	Frontend / Backend	Status	Resolution date	Notes
59	Website Homepage	Add a more powerful CTA to become a member in the Home Page	28/04/2023	EAAE	Frontend	To discuss further		HP CTA changes depending on the highlight of the period
60	Website Homepage	Add a short mission description of the project	28/04/2023	EAAE	Frontend	To discuss further		
61	Website Homepage	Make content more visual (more original images and graphics). See: https://bauhaus-seas.eu for inspiration	28/04/2023	EAAE	Frontend	To discuss further		More of a comment than a real issue to address
62	Website Homepage	Explore ways to dynamically showcase and engage the community: forum? Europe map with solutions? Comments do not seem a very engaging way. See: https://www.webdesign-inspiration.com/web-designs/industry/community	28/04/2023	EAAE	Frontend	To discuss further		More discussions within the consortium are needed
63	Website UI/UX	Make it possible to edit published content from user profile	28/04/2023	EAAE	Frontend	Done	11/05/2023	
64	Website UI/UX	Substitute Comment section in tools by a more appealing interaction feature	28/04/2023	EAAE	Frontend	To discuss further		More inputs/explanation from consortium are needed
65	Website UI/UX	Work on the content hierarchy between the home page, navigation bar for the user experience	28/04/2023	EAAE	Frontend	To discuss further		A first modification was

#	Section	Issue	Insertion date	Inserted by	Frontend / Backend	Status	Resolution date	Notes
								made through UX/UI workshop inputs gathered with external users
66	Website UI/UX	Replace flipping cards everywhere on the website feature which is slow and tends to fail	28/04/2023	EAAE	Frontend	Done	05/05/2023	
67	Website UI/UX	Add short text descriptions in every category of the Early Adopter form. I.e. Adopted digital solution: In the project you are submitting, which were the digital solutions you used?	28/04/2023	EAAE	Backend	Done	21/06/2023	
68	Website UI/UX	Solve font issues at "Adopted digital solution" privacy policy and captcha	28/04/2023	EAAE	Frontend	Blocked		More clarifications needed
69	Website UI/UX	Develop a more engaging Website Copy and Tone of Voice in our website texts, automatic emails, social media posts etc. What kind of community personality are we creating?	28/04/2023	TU DELFT	Frontend	To discuss further		More discussions within the consortium are needed
70	Website UI/UX	Flip cards are still displaying erratic behaviour in Safari	05/05/2023	TU DELFT	Frontend	Done	05/05/2023	
71	Website UI/UX	Menu starts to crumble on tablets using landscape format. Menu names start to fold and move into the logo	05/05/2023	TU DELFT	Frontend	Done	11/05/2023	

#	Section	Issue	Insertion date	Inserted by	Frontend / Backend	Status	Resolution date	Notes
72	Website UI/UX	User experience, visual language and overall graphic design is of low quality and is far away what designers, architect expect to use	05/05/2023	TU DELFT	Frontend	To discuss further		NEB style guide might not allow its realisation. More discussions needed from consortium
73	Digital Toolkit	Adding tools to the toolkit is counter intuitive. When you click on preview, then the content that you have added is gone.	05/05/2023	TU DELFT	Backend	Done	11/05/2023	
74	eLearning Platform	There is a structural lack of co-design and user consultation. Regarding the Elearning platform, once more we are presented with a solution that has not been discussed before.	05/05/2023	TU DELFT	Frontend	Done	05/05/2023	
75	eLearning Platform	Better explain what the TRUST-LCMS is	05/05/2023	TU DELFT	Backend	Done	05/05/2023	
76	Digital Toolkit	Search in the TOOLKIT doesn't work, it only picks up the title of the tool but no text in the description, as such it is pretty pointless. I can search for Honeybee but not for the technologies used in Honeybee	05/05/2023	TU DELFT	Frontend	In progress		Will be implemented in Rel 2.1
77	eLearning Platform	Search in the eLearning courses doesn't work, it only picks up the title of the tool but no text in the description, as such it is pretty pointless	05/05/2023	TU DELFT	Frontend	In progress		Will be implemented in Rel. 2.1
78	Website UI/UX	The overall website doesn't have search	05/05/2023	TU DELFT	Frontend	In progress		Will be implemented in

#	Section	Issue	Insertion date	Inserted by	Frontend / Backend	Status	Resolution date	Notes
								Rel. 2.1
79	eLearning Platform	Flipping cards do not work. Maybe we should take them off the whole website	31/03/2023	EAAE	Backend	Done	11/05/2023	
80	eLearning Platform	Remove login when being redirected to the catalogue	31/03/2023	EAAE	Backend	Done	11/05/2023	
81	eLearning Platform	Make it more visual using images or videos on the front page. Graphic style as digiNEB.eu website	31/03/2023	EAAE	Backend	To do		More inputs from partners is needed
82	eLearning Platform	Quiz at the end of the course. Hoping that after responding to 5 questions, data showing which questions were correctly and incorrectly answered would be available.	03/04/2023	InnovaWood	Backend	To do		Will be implemented as more original courses will be uploaded
83	eLearning Platform	No access to add content to digiNEB Moodle (Ex 74)	08/05/2023	TU DELFT	Frontend	Done	10/05/2023	
84	eLearning Platform	No copyright declaration in digiNEB Moodle (Ex 76)	08/05/2023	TU DELFT	Frontend	Done	10/05/2023	
85	eLearning Platform	digiNEB Moodle doesn't have Terms of Use. (Ex. 70)	08/05/2023	TU DELFT	Frontend	Done	10/05/2023	
86	eLearning Platform	digiNEB Moodle lacks Data retention policy. (Ex 75)	08/05/2023	TU DELFT	Frontend	Done	10/05/2023	

#	Section	Issue	Insertion date	Inserted by	Frontend / Backend	Status	Resolution date	Notes
87	eLearning Platform	(Ex 69) Update website terms of use under Creative Commons Licence CC BY 4.0	08/05/2023	TU DELFT	Frontend	Done	05/06/2023	
88	eLearning Platform	Create manual on how to add content	08/05/2023	TU DELFT	Frontend	Done	08/05/2023	

Appendix B

Rolling Excel sheet containing comments from the digiNEB.eu external UX/UI workshop (June 2023).

#	Website section	Type of issue	Status	Notes
1	Homepage	Feature a NEB compass for use cases	TBD	Will be implemented in Rel 3.0 as the project matures and gains more content
2	Information Architecture	Show the ecosystem & stakeholders	TBD	Will be implemented in Rel 3.0 as the project matures and gains more content
3	General	Missing networking capabilities Networking functionality (where to find people & companies who already have experienced my challenge and can provide guidance to me?)	TBD	Needs further discussions
4	Digital Toolkit	Add a rating/review system to toolkit solutions	Blocked	Possible IP problems as the digiNEB.eu consortium is promoting solutions as they appear on the website
5	Information Architecture	Missing section showcasing current challenges for cities and communities	TBD	Will be implemented in Rel 3.0 as the project matures and gains more content
6	Top Menu	Acronyms (TWGs, EAG) are not clear	Done	
7	Top Menu	"Platform" is not clear as a label	Done	

#	Website section	Type of issue	Status	Notes
8	Top Menu	EAG looks out of place, outside the "About" menu	Done	
9	Top Menu	dropdown arrows are placed between elements like separators (don't look tied to the item on their left)	Done	
10	Top Menu/Footer Menu	Add "contact" menu item	Done	
11	Footer Menu	Add "FAQ" menu item	TBD	Will be implemented in Rel 3.0 as the project matures and gains more content
12	Information Architecture	Add how-to section	TBD	Will be implemented in Rel 3.0 as the project matures and gains more content
13	Top Menu	Remove observatory from top menu	Done	
14	Top Menu	Restructure the top menu	Done	
15	eLearning Platform	Add a filter for private vs public sector	Blocked	Not compatible with already present filters
16	eLearning Platform	Explain how (and who) can recommend/add training material	Done	
17	Digital Toolkit	Review and expand the filtering options for the digital toolkit. Proposed options: interoperability (integration w/ existing tools); projects where it's been applied; companies that have used it; CO2 impact; financial impact; user rating; sector/domain (building, food, textile, smart cities, health, etc); technology the	TBD	Will be implemented in Rel 3.0 as the project matures and gains more content

#	Website section	Type of issue	Status	Notes
		solution is based on (IoT, blockchain, AI, etc); the 3 principles and the 4 thematic axes of NEB; status (design, in process, finished); places/countries where it's been implemented; price; TRL/MRL; size of the population/company where it's been used; business area (architecture, engineering, sustainability, etc);		
18	Digital Toolkit	Insert a compass-like scoring to represent multi-dimensional scores	Blocked	Possible IP problems as the digiNEB.eu consortium is promoting solutions as they appear on the website. Also digital solutions can be commented in Thematic Working Groups discussions
19	Digital Toolkit	Allow users to add reviews to "products" in the catalogue	Blocked	Possible IP problems as the digiNEB.eu consortium is promoting solutions as they appear on the website. Also digital solutions can be commented in Thematic Working Groups discussions
20	eLearning Platform	Review and expand the filtering options for the e-learning area. Proposed options: topic; sector; user role in the project; user stage in the project; goal of the learning (e.g. I want to be an experienced BIM operator in Virtual Environments); user rating; provider; price; country; technology; skill; certification earned; the 3 principles and the 4 thematic axes of NEB; difficulty; language; duration; format (online / in-person);	Blocked	Possible UX/UI problems might arise by adding too many filtering options
21	eLearning Platform	Add a "GIS" option under the "technology" category	Done	
22	eLearning Platform	Add a self-evaluation tool to get direction to the recommended e-learning	Blocked	Possible IP problems as the digiNEB.eu

#	Website section	Type of issue	Status	Notes
		courses, also in terms of goal e.g. building an expertise/career path (ex. I want to be an experienced BIM operator in Virtual Environments), leading to an eventual certification		consortium is promoting solutions as they appear on the website. Also the training material can be commented in Thematic Working Groups discussions
23	Digital Toolkit	A sorting option is missing	Done	
24	Digital Toolkit	The information in result cards is not enough. expand it with 3-6 main criteria (see filtering categories + compass-like widget)	Done	
25	Digital Toolkit	The "proprietary" tag in result cards is not clear	Done	
26	Digital Toolkit	The "type of solution" filter category is not clear: has it to do with technology or application?	Done	
27	Digital Toolkit	change the "for whom" filter category to "I am"	Blocked	Possible UX/UI problems might arise
28	Digital Toolkit	Use the "funded by the EU" badge as a filter	Done	
29	Digital Toolkit	swap the left and right columns in listing pages	Blocked	Possible UX/UI problems might arise
30	Success Stories	The option to add/recommend success stories is not enough visible, at the end of the page	Done	
31	Success Stories	Add filters to success stories. Proposed options: topic; role of the visitor in the process; technology used; interoperability solution applied; country; challenge tackled (e.g. climate change, circular economy, biodiversity loss, regenerative agriculture, etc); 4 thematic axes	TBD	Will be implemented in Rel 3.0 as the project matures and gains more content

#	Website section	Type of issue	Status	Notes
32	Success Stories	Show sorting criteria	Done	
33	Success Stories	Add tags to the success stories cards	Done	
34	Success Stories	Make it clear that there's more to read, e.g. "..." at the end	Done	
35	Success Stories	Explain the criteria and the process of curation / review of the success stories	TBD	Will be implemented in Rel 3.0 as the project matures and gains more content
36	Success Stories	Distinguish individual projects and initiatives	Blocked	Out of scope with the filters currently in place for success stories
37	Success Stories	The NEB principles are mentioned at the beginning of the page, but not linked	Done	
38	Success Stories	Consider adding a visual map of where the success stories are located	Blocked	Out of scope as many success stories refer to solutions implemented in multiple location which would make a possible map extremely confusing
39	Success Stories	Don't use the words "The EU-funded project" in teaser-texts	Blocked	Out of scope as this is a EU-funded project so it is natural to explicitly mention other EU-funded initiatives/solutions
40	eLearning Platform	The introductory text invites to "share knowledge", but there is no button to do so	Done	

#	Website section	Type of issue	Status	Notes
41	eLearning Platform	Add the trainer's name and affiliation in result cards	Done	
42	eLearning Platform	Show sorting criteria	Done	
43	eLearning Platform	All GIST short descriptions in result cards are identical	Blocked	Out of scope as this was an explicit request from the course provider
44	eLearning Platform	Consider adding video introductions for courses	Blocked / TBD	This is up to the course provider, the digiNEB.eu project can only do so with courses explicitly promoted by the consortium, which could be done once the project gains more content
45	eLearning Platform	Show a 3-6 criteria and how each result scores against them (e.g. difficulty level)	Blocked / TBD	This is up to the course provider, the digiNEB.eu project can only do so with courses explicitly promoted by the consortium, which could be done once the project gains more content
46	eLearning Platform	Consider adding a closing CtA at the bottom of the page, like it's in the other listing pages (toolkit, stories)	Done	
47	General	Inconsistency in listing pages introductory text column width: wide on success stories, short on toolkit	Blocked	Out of scope as these are different items and therefore their listing display is different
49	Observatory	The observatory is not understood and perceived as hectic, messy and confusing	TBD	The observatory might become clearer

#	Website section	Type of issue	Status	Notes
				in Rel. 3.0 after more strategic content is gained. This will depend on how the project goes in the following months
50	Observatory	"What's inside the box" is a confusing label	Done	
51	Observatory	The date filters are confusing and seem not to be working as expected	Done	
52	Observatory	The date filters seems not to be working as expected	Done	
53	Observatory	Instead of using start/end date filters, categorise as ongoing/closed	Blocked	Out of scope as the observatory works like a feed platform, not a catalogue likewise other items of the digiNEB.eu digital hub (e.g. digital toolkit, success stories, eLearning platform)